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**THE EFFECTS OF POLYPHENOL-RICH FIBRE CONSUMPTION
ON TOTAL CONCENTRATIONS OF PLASMA CHOLESTEROL –
USING A PIG MODEL**

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ABSTRACT

The effects of dietary polyphenol-rich fibers on human health have been extensively discussed in the context of prevention against metabolic syndromes. Recently, the health-promoting effects of polyphenolic compounds, specifically anthocyanins and dietary fiber rich black carrots have gained increasing attentions across science and research community. Black carrot polyphenols and fibers can contribute to minimal weight gain and low total cholesterol level in blood through extending digesta transit time, reducing body fat mass and transporting bound-polyphenols relatively intact to the colon, where those released and metabolized by gut biome. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of black carrot polyphenol-rich fiber consumption on total concentrations of plasma cholesterol – using pig as a model. This study analyzed past samples from a comprehensive feeding study. The diets with added black carrot had markedly larger particle size ($p < 0.05$). No significant difference existed in weight gain and total plasma cholesterol concentrations between the dietary treatments ($p > 0.05$). However, the trend of results demonstrated a positive indication that the inclusion of black carrots into diet caused change in weight gain and plasma cholesterol level. These results suggest that polyphenols, mainly anthocyanins and fiber rich black carrots had beneficial effects on management of weight and blood cholesterol concentrations, irrespective of fat content of the diets.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

AME	Apparent metabolized energy
DF	Dietary fiber
Df*	Dilution factor
DN	<i>de novo</i>
F&V	Fruit & Vegetables
FFA	Free fatty acid
GIT	Gastrointestinal tract
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HMGC	3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA
HFD	High fat diet
LDL	Low density lipoproteins
LFD	Low fat diet
LSD	Least significant difference
ME	Metabolizable energy
NDC	Non-digestible carbohydrate
PSD	Particle size distribution
RFU	Relative fluorescence unit
SCFA	Short chain fatty acids
TDF	Total dietary fiber
TCA	Total concentrations of anthocyanins

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Research

The health-promoting effects of a high dietary intake of fruit and vegetables (F&V) are well established. Aune et al. (2017) conducted a comprehensive study to examine the F&V consumption and all-cause mortality relationship. The results suggest the inverse relationship between intake of F&V and all-cause mortality. The relationship between dietary fiber (DF) and the health of bowel was developed in the early 1950s when Denis Burkitt found that the digestive disorders that were commonly suffered by the English populations, almost never exist in African tribes eating a high plant-based diet (Burkitt, Walker & Painter 1972). This initiated extensive epidemiological studies in the 1970s that demonstrated a strong relationship between high intake of DF and declined digesta time and constipation. Furthermore, the effects of DF are not only limited to the bowel health but also binding polyphenols, leading to a transport to the colon (Gharras 2009; Pandey & Rizvi 2009).

More recent researches propose that polyphenols are also essential for health of colon (Saura-Calixto 2011; Marin et al. 2015). Binding to polyphenols of plant fibers significantly contributes to the improved ecology of the gut flora and hormonal response via colonic fermentation, producing smaller and more bioavailable short-chain fatty acids (SCFA) (Marin et al. 2015; Mosele, Macià & Motilva 2015; Popa et al. 2017). This indicates the beneficial effects of DF and bound polyphenols relationship on the gut microbiome, leading to investigation into mechanistic behavior to better understand the binding ability to polyphenols of DF. A recent study showed that 60 – 80% of black carrot anthocyanins is bound to cell wall during cell rupture, but only 2% released in the upper gastrointestinal digestion (Padayachee et al. 2013). This shows that a large proportion of black carrot anthocyanins bind to plant fibres and traffics to the colon. Day et al. (2012) evaluated the caecal fermentation rate and found that SCFA production was influenced by diet particle size.

The health benefits of polyphenol-rich fibres from plants on host health are two-fold. Firstly, the effects of fibers and the particle size on digestion and colonic fermentation and secondly, bound polyphenols reach the colon. However, the effects of fibers, polyphenols and the particle size as well as bound polyphenols on host health are not fully understood, especially in *in-vivo* setting. The research into the effects of polyphenol-rich fibre from black carrot consumption on the total plasma cholesterol concentrations – using a pig model will fulfill the research gap, and will give an advantageous insight into the beneficial roles of a plant-based diet on the host health through improved colonic health. Furthermore, the use of a pig model, obviously aimed at linking to a study on human in the future.

1.2. Organisation of the Thesis

This chapter consists of the background of research together with the organisation of thesis. Chapter 2 reviews relevant literatures. Chapter 3 presents the hypothesis, overall aim and the objectives whilst chapter 4 describes material, methods and data analyses. Chapter 5 and chapter 6 present results and discussion. Finally, chapter 7 covers the conclusion and future studies.

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are three major parts of literature being reviewed across this chapter. Those include: 1. the effects of dietary components (i.e. DF, polyphenols and diet particles) on health, 2. the underlying effects and metabolisms of those components in weight and blood cholesterol management, and finally, 3. reasons for using pig as a model to mimic human's digestive system.

Section 1: Diet

2.1. Functional Components in Black Carrot

After potatoes, carrots are the second most popular vegetable. Even though orange carrots are very common, consumption of black carrots is currently on the rise in Western Europe (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010). Despite widespreading of black carrot cultivation in some countries, research into this vegetable has been largely reported Australia, Turkey and Germany (Zadernowski 2010). In addition to the emergence of beneficial fibers and antioxidants such as vitamin E and C, black carrot attracts the attention from research community because of high content of polyphenolic components that markedly help increase antioxidant activities (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010). The major attribute of this vegetable is of intense black color from anthocyanins. Beyond pigment contributor, anthocyanins also can contribute to the variety of health benefits. In this section, the review is focused on black carrot fiber content, followed by on polyphenolic compounds, and especially anthocyanins.

2.1.1. Fibers

Dietary fibers content in black carrots may be different from one to another cultivar, and due to effects of processing and storage (Slavin & Lloyd 2012). There is a significant difference in fiber values reported in literatures as well as in food reference tables, and supposedly because of different fiber analysis methods applied. Reports of total dietary fiber (TDF) values range between 2.42-6.4% (Esatbeyoglu et al. 2016), whilst other found values include 2.5%, 2.8%, 3.4%, 3.63% and 4.4% (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010; Kamiloglu et al. 2015). The hemicellulose, cellulose and insoluble fibers account for the greatest fraction (50-92%) of TDF with lignin just only 4% (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010). The soluble fibers comprise of pectin and fermentable hemicellulose amounting to 8-50% of TDF (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010).

2.1.2. Polyphenolic Compounds and Anthocyanin Profile

Black carrots accommodate phenolic compounds with a single aromatic ring, namely phenolic acids (Montilla et al. 2011). Algarra et al. (2014) found 11 different phenolic acids and their total concentrations are greatest in the black carrot. The major phenolic compounds in black carrots are the five anthocyanins. These phenolic compounds are hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives developed by cinnamic acids esterification (Montilla et al. 2011). Currently, increasing evidences indicate that consumption of hydroxycinnamic and caffeic acids in black carrot has been linked to decreased chronic diseases (Garcia-Herrera et al. 2016). Moreover, research estimates about 30% intestinal absorption of these compounds and large metabolism of the remainder by the gut bacteria (Garcia-Herrera et al. 2016).

Black carrots contain polyphenols approximately 38%, the second highest content after the potato (Montilla et al. 2011). These polyphenols are mainly in ester form and are related to cell wall components (Guldiken et al. 2017). Those exhibit cross-linking capacity to strengthen stability of their structures in the matrix of cell walls (Guldiken et al. 2017). The bound polyphenols can escape the digestion in upper gastrointestinal and can be released in the colon where they contribute to beneficial health outcomes. Abdel-Moemin (2016) suggested that black carrots can release their polyphenols about one-half in the colon, while other vegetables can be one-fourth via colonic fermentation (**Fig. 1**).

FIGURE 1. Phases that DF and bound polyphenols are digested; finally polyphenols are released about one-half in colon via fermentation by the gut biome. (Padayachee et al. 2013).

In black carrots, anthocyanins are the main polyphenolic components that include an anthocyanidin backbone, the flavylium cation (which sometimes refers to as 2-phenylbenzopyrylium). There are six typical anthocyanidin backbones identified such as cyanidin, pelargonidin, petunidin, peonidin, delphinidin and malvidin (Barba-Espín et al. 2017). Differences between these backbones can be due to the position and number of methoxyl groups, hydroxyl groups, and number, type and position of linked sugar molecules that could be acylated by different aliphatic acids or aromatic acids (Algarra et al. 2014).

The anthocyanins identified in black carrots are the primary cyanidin derivatives (**Fig. 2**), but peonidin and pelargondin glycosides have been found as well (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010). These pigments in black carrots do not possess direct influence on their flavor. Analyzes focusing on this vegetable has determined five important anthocyanin derivatives, including cyanidin-3-(2''-xylose-6''-(4-coumaroyl) glucose-galactoside) (Cy3XCGG), cyanidin-3-(2''-xylose-6''-feruloyl-glucose-galactoside) (Cy3XFGG), cyanidin-3-(2''-xylose-6''-sinapoyl-glucose-galactoside) (Cy3XS GG), cyanidin-3-(2''-xylose-galactoside) (Cy3XG), cyanidin-3-(2''-xylose-6-glucose-galactoside) (Cy3XGG) (Gläbgen et al. 1992).

cyanidin

Where R:

2''-xylose-6''-galactoside

2''-xylose-6''-glucose-galactoside

2''-xylose-6''-sinapoyl-glucose-galactoside

2''-xylose-6''-feruloyl-glucose-galactoside

2''-xylose-6''-(4-coumaroyl)glucose-galactoside

FIGURE 2. The main polyphenols that are commonly quantified in black carrots include 5 anthocyanins. The basic anthocyanin backbone is called cyaniding. The R groups are various glycosides. (Gläbgen et al. 1992).

Total concentration of anthocyanin (TCA) in the black carrots' roots may differ largely between and even within a cultivar depending on the coloring degree of its roots (Algarra et al. 2014). Published total content of anthocyanin ranges from 300 – 350 mg/100 g fresh weight in dark black carrots (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010). For comparison, TCA = 48 mg/100g, 113 mg/100g and 117 mg/100g in raspberries, cherries, and blueberries, respectively (Lohachoompol, Srzednicki & Craske 2004). In the American diet, the everyday anthocyanin intake is approximately 12.5 mg per day (Arscott & Tanumihardjo 2010). The black carrots' anthocyanins constitute the essential antioxidant ability.

2.1.3. Binding of Polyphenols to the Plant's Cell Wall and The Effects of Processing

First, the food matrix-attached polyphenols, i.e. anthocyanins (**Fig. 3**) have to be released from the cell wall materials prior to the solubilization and assimilation into micellar structures of lipid for uptake into mucosal cells of the intestine (Park et al. 2009). Anthocyanins are absorbed and available for use for storage and/or in physiological functions. Studies have proposed that the carrot matrix exhibits undesired impacts on anthocyanins absorption (Park et al. 2016). Plasma response to chronic and acute carrot feeding has shown the reduction of bioavailability compared to purified anthocyanins (Park et al. 2009).

Several food matrix constituents in black carrots dislocate the bioavailability of anthocyanins. From a ferret model, findings show the crystalline form of anthocyanins in the root cytoplasm and fibers of carrots impact on the bioavailability (Novotny, Clevidence & Kurilich 2011). Comprehensive *in-vitro* study modeling the gastric setting evinces that membrane-bound anthocyanins in chloroplasts of spinach resist stronger to the oil solubilization than the free crystalline and membrane-bound anthocyanins in the anthocyanin bodies of black carrots (Zozio, Pallet & Dornier 2011). Conversely, blanching that cause a disruption for most organelle, can improve solubilization of anthocyanins from homogenized spinach by > 60%, but has been

proved to have minor effects on anthocyanins solubilization in the black carrot juice (Park et al. 2016).

In raw black carrot juice, cell walls are taken out and cellular materials containing chromoplasts are damaged (Hiemori, Koh & Mitchell 2009). Boiling of black carrot juice more distorts the membrane-bound anthocyanins, but not anthocyanin crystals (Park et al. 2016). This leads to a hypothesis that the interactions between anthocyanins and anthocyanins in the crystals are more stable against solubilization than the interactions between lipoprotein and anthocyanins of the boiled spinach (Park et al. 2016). This is also corresponding to the finding that heating of black carrot juice showed no a remarkable effect on the bioavailability of anthocyanins in the ferrets. (Sevimli-Gur et al. 2013).

FIGURE 3. Polyphenols such as anthocyanins become bound to cell wall and released when cell rupture. (Park et al. 2016)

In the duodenal model, solubilization of anthocyanins into the incorporated micelle for black carrot juice anthocyanins was the lowest (Zozio, Pallet & Dornier 2011). This suggested that the more apolar anthocyanins leftover in the food matrix appear to be less available for absorption. As expressed above, food processing/preparation, namely heating, enzymatic and mechanical treatments, leads to softening and disrupting the organelle and plant cell wall (Park et al. 2016). Pureeing vegetables results in surface area enlargement and particle size reduction that can improve the anthocyanins availability to the colonic lumen. The detachment from the food matrix prior to absorption has been known as bioaccessibility (Park et al. 2016). Plasma response of anthocyanins from only one meal of ground/raw black carrots was higher than that from the cooked black carrots (65.1 and $41.4 \pm 7.4\%$, respectively). Mild heat application, such as blanching the black carrots resulted in a minor or almost no improvement in anthocyanin absorption in calves (Sevimli-Gur et al. 2013). In a population-based study, a 4-week feeding of thermally cooked and pureed black carrots and spinach accrued plasma anthocyanins three-folds

lower than that of the ground formats (Devi, Kumar & Da 2012). In healthy adults, from only one meal test, anthocyanin elicited greater bioavailability in order as follows: raw-diced carrot > boiled-mashed carrot > commercially puréed (thermally treated) carrot (Hiemori, Koh & Mitchell 2009).

Another associated component of the black carrot matrix is anthocyanin-protein complexes (Sevimli-Gur et al. 2013). Heating to denature these complexes could increase bioavailability of anthocyanins (Hiemori, Koh & Mitchell 2009). Anthocyanins binding proteins have been found in the chromoplasts of black carrot roots. However, because of their minimal association with the total anthocyanins of black carrots, they are unlikely to have any significant effects on the anthocyanins bioavailability (Hiemori, Koh & Mitchell 2009). Table 1 summarizes the main factors that affect the polyphenols bioavailability.

Table 1. Major determinants affecting the bioavailability of dietary polyphenols	
External factors	Environmental factors; food availability
Food Processing related factors	Thermal treatments; homogenization; liophylization; cooking and methods of culinary preparation; storage
Food related factors	Food matrix; presence of positive or negative effectors of absorption (i.e. fat, fiber)
Interaction with other compounds	Bonds with proteins (i.e. albumin) or with polyphenols with similar mechanism of absorption
Polyphenols related factors	Chemical structure; concentration in food; amount introduced
Host related factors	Intestinal factors (i.e. enzyme activity; intestinal transit time; colonic microflora). Systemic factors (i.e. gender and age; disorders and/or pathologies; genetics; physiological condition)

Source: Sevimli-Gur et al. (2013)

2.2. Swine Diet Particle Size

At the time of grinding the diet components (i.e. especially cereals, fruit and vegetables), the feed particle size distribution (PSD) that necessarily needed can be attained (Lv et al. 2015). According to the published data from existing research, the optimal PSD of diets for pigs is in the area of medium-sized particles, ranging from 500 – 1600 µm, and whilst those that < 400 µm have been thought as unfavorable because of potential impacts on the health of gut (Angulo, Brufau & Esteve-Garcia 1996). However, the optimal size of diets' particles is mainly influenced by the complexity of diets, added fat, grain types and animal age (Lv et al. 2015). Through making changes in the feed ingredient compositions, the characteristics of feed particle size are surely modified. Merkus (2008) suggested that the relative effects of typical fibers and cereal sources are more significant than those of lipid and protein sources. For fiber, the change in mean/average of particle size in a hundred unit of ingredient was in the range of 2.3 – 21.6 µm, and of 15 – 16 µm for the cereal sources, while for protein source the range was between 0 – 5.2

μm and biggest range from lipid source was 1.8 – 2.2 μm (Angulo, Brufau & Esteve-Garcia 1996).

Carré et al. (2002) found that the optimal size of particles of sorghum and corn in nursery phase that necessarily considered about the pig's integrity of gastric mucosa, is around 500 μm . For wheat-based diets, the optimal mean of their particle size is about 600 μm , as determined by (Ivashchenko & Ivashchenko 2014). Likewise, Hanrahan (1984) reported the range of optimal particle size for growing-finishing pigs is 500 –700 μm . According to Lv et al. (2015), slightly finer particles have the mean particle size of 400 –600 μm . Corn, sorghum, barley and wheat that are ground to have particle size < 700 μm can increase energy and nitrogen digestibility, and although the particle size increased (i.e. 700 –1500 μm), there is no significant difference in nutritional values of the milled cereal grains. This leads to a suggestion that the particle size of 600 –700 μm is ideal for both nutritive yields and the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) health (Angulo, Brufau & Esteve-Garcia 1996). High fiber cereal, fruit and vegetables have to be ground more finely to improve the value of feeding. These ingredients can become more attractive and be used instead of corn when they have been ground to the size of about 700 μm . A study of Gabriel, Mallet & Leconte (2003), on a comparison between more uniform PSD diets and higher PSD variation diets, showed that nutrient values and absorption of the feed is also affected by the uniformity of the feed particle size.

Section 2: Effects and Metabolism

2.3. Health Essentials of Dietary Fibers

The significance of fibers from black carrot for digestion system has been recently recognized. Bystrická et al. (2015) have advanced the 'fiber hypothesis', stating that consumption of higher fiber diets from black carrots helps prevent a variety of Western diseases. Dietary fiber is necessarily soluble and insoluble in the diets. The insoluble fibers are potentially fermented in the large intestine (Anguita et al. 2007). Whilst there is a few fibers (i.e. purified cellulose) may escape from fermentation, others such as pectin and inulin are completely fermented by the colonic microflora (Flisikowska et al. 2017). Soluble fiber have been exhibited the beneficial effects on lowering cholesterol levels in blood, and insoluble fiber helps improve stool weight and transport bound polyphenols intact to the colon. Despite some inconsistency in finding, the majority of scientific evidences have been supporting these health-promoting properties (Bystrická et al. 2015; Flisikowska et al. 2017).

In terms of physiological benefits of fiber, more current studies have found that additional attributes including fermentability and viscosity are the major aspects (Lattimer & Haub 2010). Fermentable fibers are those that the gut microbiome can metabolize, and viscous fibers are those that form gel in the GIT (Uzomah & Ofuya 2009). Generally, soluble fibers are more thoroughly fermented and more viscous than insoluble fibers. But, not all soluble fibers are viscous, and a few of insoluble ones may be highly fermentable (Uzomah & Ofuya 2009). Like starch, fibers consist of many sugar units binding to together. However, unlike most starch, sugar bonds in fibers cannot be cleaved by enzymes in digestive system, and eventually pass intact to the colon (Slavin 2013). There, fibers are fermented and contributing to the production of SCFA (**Fig. 4**), thereby being absorbed and utilized in the body (Lee et al. 2015).

FIGURE 4. Upon arrival in the colon, dietary fiber is fermented by gut microbiome, producing certain SCFAs namely acetate, propionate, and butyrate. These SCFAs benefit host health in many ways, and the major two benefits include reduce weight gain (due to inducing satiety) and the level of very low and low-density lipoproteins (VLDL/LDL). Source: Lee et al. (2015)

In addition, difference in dietary fiber composition can result in shifting the digestion site in both pig and human (Pietruszka, Jacyno & Kolodzie 2008). Consequently, this changes the resident microbiome community, either by both intensifying the numbers and diversifying the SCFA-producing responsible bacteria, or in some cases by decreasing the number of pathogenic bacteria (Anguita et al. 2007). The mechanism behind the latter remains unclear, but it can be due to pH level changed during fermentation, bacterial-inhibitory effects of SCFA, or the microbial-binding properties of certain fibers (Hopwood et al. 2004). They also found that enhanced SCFA concentrations in the gut, particularly acetate could contribute to the preventive effect on *Escherichia coli* overgrowth.

The increase in the numbers and diversity of bacteria responsible for SCFA production leads to the different SCFA levels in different colonic regions and feces. As aforementioned above, because of SCFA serving as the main energy source of epithelial cells, it has been suggested that elevated concentrations of SCFA can lengthen the colon through growth stimulation of epithelial cells (O'Connell, Beattie & Weatherup 2002). Moreover, elevated butyric concentration

produced in responding to fibers is related to declined epithelial apoptosis in the colon and increased expression of the caecal SCFA monocarboxylate-transporter I (Anguita et al. 2007).

However, the increased SCFA levels are not a healthy GIT indicator since these microbially-produced SCFA have to be absorbed and exploited by the epithelial cells (Hopwood et al. 2004). Flisikowska et al. (2017) indicate that the production of propionate and butyrate in responding to various fibers are absorbed by the mucosa in the colon at different efficacies, and consequently constitutes the major health benefits. Overall, these variations mimic those investigated in human, and have been positively indicated to help reduce total cholesterol level in blood and prevent colon cancer (Flisikowska et al. 2017). Until today, there have been so limited studies assessing the effects of SCFA supplementation or polyphenol-rich fibers on blood cholesterol profile reduction using a porcine model.

2.4. Anthocyanins and Health

In a research of Barba-Espín et al. (2017), black carrots have been found abundant in anthocyanins that have greater antioxidant ability than other carrot species such as yellow and orange carrots. Anthocyanins are pigments that water-soluble consisting a group of more than 600 compounds constituting black, blue and red color in many fruit and vegetables (Montilla et al. 2011). In plants, function of anthocyanins is providing photoprotection and scavenging free radicals and so on. Moreover, dietary anthocyanins may play a potential role in health improvement and protection against certain cancers and cardiovascular diseases (**Fig. 5**) by acting like dietary antioxidants, apoptosis, phase II enzymes, stimulating induction of vasoprotective and anti-inflammatory effects, and reducing lipid oxidation and inflammation (Khandare et al. 2011).

FIGURE 5. Bioavailability, metabolism and atheroprotective effects of anthocyanins

Source: Khandare et al. (2011)

Bioavailability of dietary anthocyanins seems to be quite low. Analysis of urinary recoveries of bioavailable anthocyanins indicates a range from 0.004 – 0.1% of intake (Mcghie & Stevenson 2013). Studies on bioavailability of anthocyanins in human subjects using different processing formats of black carrots: cooked puréed, whole raw, and juice have indicated that anthocyanins in black carrots become bioavailable and absorbable relatively intact, but however with low

efficiency (Charron et al. 2009). Furthermore, results from these feeding studies propose that the saturation of the cyaniding-based anthocyanins absorption from black carrots takes place between intakes of 250 – 350 μmol (~150 – 250 g black carrots). The proportional recovery of acylated anthocyanins is lower than nonacylated anthocyanins in studies with both black carrot juice and whole black carrots (Charron et al. 2009; Mcghie & Stevenson 2013). From this result, it is suggested that not the plant matrix, but the acylation that has direct effects on the bioavailability of black carrots (Charron et al. 2009). At the same time, increasing recent studies report that gut microflora can release and metabolize the bound anthocyanins, producing more bioavailable and smaller end-products /SCFA via colonic fermentation (Mazza & Kay 2008; Bobrich et al. 2014).

2.5. Dietary Energy and Fat on Pig Growth Performance

Influences of energy intakes on the weight gain and composition of carcass are well-documented. In linear phase relationship between the rate of growth and energy intake, fat levels in body and thickness of fat in carcass increase curvilinearly (Park et al. 2012). Elevated energy intake will always increase body weight gain. The effects of adding fat into high dietary energy diets can be seen in Table 2. In this study, castrated male pigs were fed on either a corn-soy supplemented or not supplemented with 5% fat diet for 44 days (Park et al. 2012).

Table 2. The effects of the addition of fat to corn-soy diets on the performance of barrows		
	Added fat (%)	
	0	5
Growth rate (g/d)	718 ^b	791 ^a
Weight gain (kg/week)	5.03 ^b	5.54 ^a
Row means with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)		

Source: Park et al. (2012)

Results show that, energy intake of the diet without added fat was the same as data reported by King et al. (2004), which performance almost reached maximum. However, the growth rate and weight gain increased while dietary energy elevated from 14.5 – 15.4 MJ/kg by adding fat. The feed efficiency improvement was significantly greater than relative difference in the content of dietary energy between diets, 12.6 and 6.2%, respectively. Similarly, findings from another experiment, which diet energy was increased by the addition of fat, suggested that fat is more efficiently utilized for metabolism of energy than what normally accepted (Apple et al. 2017). For instance, adding a combination of 6-8% soy hulls and enough fat to induce isoenergetic in diets with the corn-soy control diets indicated a noticeably faster rate of growth and body weight in pig, 72 – 120 kg and 75 – 95 kg, respectively (Apple et al. 2017). Besides, there was a 5% improvement in feed efficiency. These effects occur also in younger pigs, so for pig that has liveweight = 15 – 30 kg its diets are currently fiber and fat added (King et al. 2004).

Table 3 displayed the results focusing on the effects of included fat and dietary energy on the growth progress of finisher pigs. In this feeding study, the gilts and barrows were fed on corn-soy diets with different fat levels (0, 3, 6 and 9%) incorporated for 84 days (Noori et al. 2011). And, as this experiment, the housing and environment was excellently provided, so the author did not expect to see the effects of added fat that has on the growth performance. Conversely, growth rate

remained linearly corresponding to the elevated dietary content of diet energy, and the feed efficiency also improved by 2 – 6 %. In this study, carcass weight increased almost 5% when increasing dietary energy intake from 14.5 – 16.4 MJ/kg, and the thickness of back-fat of castrated males was increased when fat levels increased from 6 – 9% (Noori et al. 2011).

Table 3. The effects of the addition of fat to corn-soy diets on the performance of barrows

	Added fat (%)				Significance
	0	3	6	9	
Daily gain (g)	881	901	936	955	$p<0.05$
Weight gain (kg/week)	6.17	6.31	6.55	6.69	$p<0.05$

Source: Noori et al. (2011).

2.6. Addition of Fat and the Gut Microflora

Eating trans- and high saturated fat is considered to evoke the risk of cardiovascular disease through upregulating plasma total and LDL cholesterol (Murphy, Velazquez & Herbert 2015). However, some fats are good for health, e.g. mono- and polyunsaturated fats. Some pig feeding and human studies have reported a high-fat diet increases numbers of total anaerobic microbiota and counts of *Bacteroides* (**Table 4**) (Murphy, Velazquez & Herbert 2015). To look into more specific effects of various dietary fats on the gut microflora in human, Kuda et al. (2017) offered diets with different fat content added. The findings noted that low-fat diet consumption resulted in an increased profusion of *Bifidobacterium* in feces, together with reduced total cholesterol level and fasting glucose comparing to the baseline. But, a high-saturated fat diet increased *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* proportions. Human subjects with high-unsaturated fat content did not encounter the change in bacterial genera abundance, but had overall declined microbial load, blood total- and LDL cholesterol (Kuda et al. 2017).

A study in pigs has shown that the consumption of a high-fat diet results in more *Clostridiales*, *Bacteroides*, and *Enterobacteriales* (that are acetate and propionate producing species), and less *Lactobacillus intestinalis* (Pedersen et al. 2013). And, the profusion of *Lactobacillus intestinalis* is due to a negative correlation with body weight and fat mass of the pigs. Change in bacterial genera has been reported to control metabolic endotoxemia-induced inflammation in pigs fed with high-fat diets (Heinritz et al. al 2016). Porcine studies have compared as well the differential impacts of different fats on the gut microbiota.

Table 4. Effects of fats on gut biome							
	<i>Lactic acid bacteria</i>	<i>Bifidobacteria</i>	<i>Clostridiales</i>	<i>Bacteroides</i>	<i>Bilophila</i>	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>
Low fat		↑					
High fat	↓		↑	↑			
High saturated fat				↑	↑	↑	
High unsaturated fat	↑	↑					↑

Source: Murphy, Velazquez & Herbert (2015)

A comparison of fish-oil derived and lard-derived lipids showed that the former increased the *Verru-comicrobia* (*Akkermansia muciniphila*), lactic acid bacteria (*Lactobacillus* and *Streptococcus*), and *Actinobacteria* (*Bi dobacterium* and *Adlercreutzia*), and the latter increased *Bacteroides* and *Bilophila* in fed pigs (Cotter 2016). Moreover, lard-fed pigs also provoked the systematic toll-like receptor activation, inflammation of white adipose tissue, and insulin sensitivity impairment compared to fish-oil fed pigs. The author suggested that these results are partly because of bacterial variations between the two groups: microflora transplantation from one group to the other. After administered by antibiotic, it both enriched the transplant gut with influential genera from the donor species and replicated the donor's metabolic and inflammatory syndrome (Cotter 2016). These findings demonstrated that the bacteria in the gut may induce metabolic inflammation through a signal of toll-like receptor on challenge with a saturated-fat rich diet.

In short, different amount and type of fat as well as fibers added into the feed/diet have differential effects on growth performance of pigs. Moreover, consumption of low-fat and high-fat diets can result in a shift in abundance of gut microbiome genera and overall reduction of cholesterol level.

2.7. Particle Size on Nutrient Utilization

It becomes a universal consensus that diet particle sizes can increase and/or reduce surface area of the substrate for enzymatic digestion, resulting in both improved gut motility and nutrient digestibility. The review in this section focuses on optimal particle size of feeds in general, followed by the influences of particle sizes and feed forms on the GIT health.

Despite the fact that the size reduction of diet particles is suggested to enhance nutrient digestibility through improving the availability of surface area to enzymes of digestion, research into association between diet particle size and digestibility of nutrients remains lacking, and in the case of cereals, are inconclusive (Cools et al. 2014). In a mash diet, the apparent metabolized energy (AME) value was increased by fine grinding of maize, but the opposite effects shown in a pelleted diet (Carré et al. 2002). Gabriel, Mallet and Leconte (2003) pointed out that finely ground wheat results in higher digestibility of starch and the AME than coarse-ground wheat.

But, coarse grinding of maize is suggested to improve lysine retention and nitrogen efficiency in pigs fed mash diets. Cools et al. (2014) stated that coarse grinding is not effective in the maize-based diets, but effective in wheat-based in terms of the AME increase. Conversely, Hetland, Svihus and Choct (2005) reported that there is no a link between particle size of wheat to the AME.

Studies show an unfavorable association between wheat hardness and the digestibility of starch in a pelleted feed (Gabriel, Mallet & Leconte 2003). The hardness contributes to larger particle size, thereby decreasing surface area and the enzymatic accessibility in digestive system (Carré et al. 2002). In contrast, Vukmirović et al. (2017) reported that endosperm hardness does not affect the AME of the wheat-based pelleted diets. Lack of association between the hardness of grains and starch digestibility and AME in mash wheat diets has been found by some other researchers (Vukmirović et al. 2017)

Studies focusing on dicotyledonous seeds show less equivocal results. Coarsely ground grain legumes have lower nutrient digestibility coefficients and energy utilization (Lebel et al. 2016). Generally, finely ground peas have been suggested to increase the total tract digestibility of protein and starch when fed as mash diets (Carré et al. 2002). Likewise, it is also reported to enhance the true ileal protein digestibility. These positive effects also occur in finely ground sweet lupine seeds (Gabriel, Mallet & Leconte 2003). These effects may attribute to the increased nutrient accessibility foundation in fine legume particles, whereas faba bean that finely ground has no influence on protein digestibility in total tract (Lebel et al. 2016). The result that is contradicted to the particle size's effects on nutrient digestibility can be due to the differences in measuring sites (i.e. between total tract and ileal). Recently, the inconsistent and altered effects of colonic microbiome are being appreciated, and agreed that the ileal digesta is the preferred method for analyzing digestibility of nutrient in pigs, rather than excreta (Lebel et al. 2016).

In terms of polyphenols and mineral availability, it is interesting to note that coarse is advantageous over fine grinding (Yamamoto et al. 2016). Large black carrots particle size has been reported to critically increase mono- and diacylated anthocyanins utilization in growing-pigs (Wolf, Rust & Kamphues 2010). Similarly, larger particle size of maize also improves phyrate phosphorous, total phosphorous and calcium utilization in pigs. Plasma anthocyanin levels of pigs were improved once coarsely black carrot fed rather than finely carrot fed (Yamamoto et al. 2016). Similar findings have been demonstrated with orange carrot fed diet (i.e. improve the carotenoid absorption). It advanced the hypothesis that the larger particle size extends transit time providing more time for polyphenols and mineral digestion and absorption (Yamamoto et al. 2016).

2.8. Influence of Particle Size and Feed Forms on Health of the Gut

To date, reasons causing the gastric epithelial modifications remain unclear, but one of the risk determinants is feed structure – that includes size of the cereal and other feed component particles (Rojas & Stein 2017). Heavy intensity of grinding is a-must consideration in the process of pelleting as regard to PSD of pig's feed. In a study of Sola-Oriol, Roura and Torrallardona (2008), bleeding ulcers, mucosal erosions and hyperkeratosis were more often identified in pelleted-diet fed pigs than those in a mashed-fed diet.

In a feeding study of Nir, Melcion and Picard (1990), pigs were fed with corn-based diets, where corn was ground to achieve different mean PSD, i.e. 1000, 800, 600 and 400 μm , and the diets were prepared in two formats: pellet and mash. Results showed that as particle size reduced and with pelleted diets, keratinization and lesion of the gastric mucosa increased, but at the same time body weight gain of pigs also markedly increased. This study concluded that 600 μm was the optimal mean diameter of diet particles for growth performance, morphology of stomach, digestibility as well as excretion of nutrients (Nir, Melcion, & Picard 1990). Correspondingly, in the research of Jerez, Zhang and Wang (2011), a finding indicated that stomach morphology was undesirably impacted when PSD < 600 μm , but as the mean PSD reduced, there was a growth improvement and declining nitrogen excretion and daily dry matters. Nir, Melcion and Picard (1990) suggested that particle size of barley ranging from 400 –1100 μm did not influence on the growth performance of pig. On the other hand, they also found that both small intestine structures and stomach mucosa integrity were impacted by fine grinding, thereby damaging the gut health in overall. Singh et al. (2016) found 600 μm wheat-ground diet fed pigs exposed more ulcer than those fed with 1200 μm wheat-ground diet. In Flis, Sobotka & Purwin (2014)'s research, PSD < 400 μm was known as fine particles, and results further showed that <20% of fine particles in diets has no effects on mucosa, but $\geq 36\%$ causes detrimental mucosa damage. According to this result, Heugten and Kempen (2002) classified ulcerogenic risk of diets into 3: Class 1 (i.e. high risk), Class 2/medium risk and Class 3/low risk, which > 36%, 29 –36%, and < 29% of particles that PSD < 400 μm , respectively.

A key aspect of the healthy GIT is a minimal level of enterobacteria (Rojas & Stein 2017). Feed physical characteristics have a powerful effect on sensitivity to *Salmonella* spp. infection in pigs. Compared to fine grinding, coarse grinding decreases the *Salmonella* spp. infection in mash-diet fed pigs. Furthermore, Morel and Cottam (2007) found that the incidence of *Salmonella* spp. increased when feeding with pelleted diet comparing to mash diet. Another comprehensive feeding study by Knap and Wang (2012) observed pigs fed with coarsely ground mash diets had much higher total anaerobic bacteria count, elevated concentrations of various organic acids and lower pH in stomach than those that fed with coarsely ground pellet, finely ground mash and finely ground pellet diets. The same findings have been reported by several other workers, such as Moreira et al. (2009), Cho, Lee and Kim (2014) and eventually concluded that the coarser of diet particle, the slower passage rate and the higher dry matter in the stomach of pigs. They also reported the material consistency in stomach of pigs fed with coarse diet that is firmer (while solid and liquid phase for fine diets). This improves the activity of gut microbiota, such as growth promotion for lactic acid bacteria as because of providing more time for bacterial multiplication in the stomach (**Fig. 6**). In addition, elevated lactic concentration and other organic acids drop pH inhibits enterobacteria (Moreira et al. 2009; Cho, Lee & Kim 2014).

If pigs are fed with a coarse diet, a large majority of starch and fibers will not be digested in duodenum and will transport to the colon. The gut microbiota will degrade/ferment those components into SCFA that may help protect against pathogenic bacteria (Moreira et al. 2009) and benefit the host health.

FIGURE 6. Coarser diet/feed containing high content of fiber, fat and protein slow down digestion providing more substrate for gut bacteria leading to an increased in bacterial multiplication and nutrient absorption. Source: Moreira et al. (2009)

Briefly, particle size of diets plays a very important role in growth performance, nutrient utilization and the health of GIT. The optimal PSD ranges from 500 to 700 μm , which is considered a coarse diet. The coarse particles can slow down the digesta transit time through digestive tracts, thereby extending the exposure time of nutrient to enzymes in the digestion that resulting in an increased in nutrient digestibility and energy utilization. Moreover, the larger particle size is beneficial for colonic bacteria in terms of fermentation to produce SCFA, lowering pH that helps inhibit the incidence of pathogenic infections.

2.9. The Effects of SCFA on Cholesterol Metabolism

SCFA influences cholesterol metabolism and adipose tissue at a few levels. In the liver, the inevitability of acetate is *de novo* (DN) cholesterologenesis and lipogenesis, but these may be prevented by propionate (Besten et al. 2013). Therefore, the propionic ratio: acetate appears to be a key contributing factor in colonic acetate to lipid stores. Increasing current findings have shown propionate per se can decrease fat profiles in both liver and visceral (Legrand et al. 2010). Elevated circulating SCFA is related to the reduction of adipogenesis and adipocytes lipolysis (Besten et al. 2013). And also, SCFA prevents insulin that triggered accumulation of lipid in adipocytes through signaling of free fatty acid receptor 2 (Heimann et al. 2016). Thus, this makes small adipocytes quite more responsive that highly linked to improved adipose inflammatory infiltrate (Heimann et al. 2016). The effects of SCFA on the decrease of cholesterol level are presented in **Fig. 7**.

Acetate may also increase the secretion of leptin in adipocytes (Zaibi et al. 2010). Leptin is a critical homeostatic signal that derived from adipose contributing to the appetite and energy balance regulations (Besten et al. 2013). The prevention of lipolysis in the adipose tissue results

in minimizing the excretion of FFA from the adipose tissue to the liver (Heimann et al. 2016). In disease such as fatty liver, FFA that are derived from adipose has been demonstrated to account for 60% of FA to the DN triglyceride synthesis in the liver, while DN lipogenesis accounts for 26% (Donnelly et al. 2005). Propionic and acetic infusion in the rectum has shown to just under 50% reductions in plasma FFA (Legrand et al. 2010).

FIGURE 7. (At the bottom part) SCFAs decrease the adipogenesis and adipocytes lipolysis in the adipose tissue resulting in the reduction of fat/cholesterol accumulation in plasma. Source: Heimann et al. (2016)

The contributing proportion of exogenous/the gut microbially derived acetate production to acetate flux for the whole body is about 44% (Fernandes, Vogt & Wolever 2014). However, how this fractional contribution is influenced by various dietary fibers and activity of the gut microbiota has not been extensively known. Growing the availability of unimportant SCFA from fiber fermentation can be a new regulation strategy of FFA flux in the obese phenotype (Yadav 2016). But, the SCFA's roles in obesity remain controversial. More research has proposed 'energy-harvesting' hypothesis, by which SCFA is assumed to supply extra calories via fermentation in the obese along with an explanation for additional gain of body weight, but at the same time, it is not in agreement with evidence found in the observational studies in human, where high-fiber diet is expected to boost production of SCFA, thereby preventing weight gain (Maskarinec et al. 2006). More human-controlled trials are urgently required for assessing the SCFA's roles in energy homeostasis and lipid turnover.

In summary, SCFA is the common finished-metabolites of fermentation of fibers that are available to bacterial community in the GIT. It denotes the key carbonic flow from the diet to the host via the biological activities of the gut microbiota, thereby eliciting its effects on host health, especially reduction of plasma cholesterol concentrations.

Section 3: Animal Model

2.10. Pig – A Model to Study the Diet-Health Associations in Humans

Research regarding human nutrition investigates the foods' mechanisms for supporting human growth, development and health (Sciascia, Daş, & Metges 2016). Although some studies human subjects can be used, the majority cannot due to ethical challenges. Otherwise, the application of a practical animal model that can be translational is importantly required. Any species that considered, as a translational animal model should have some aspects very similar to human including anatomy, genetics and physiology; consequently, any results from the studies can be comparable to that of humans (Lamarco 2012). For over a half century, the domestic pig has been a research animal, which extensively used as a translational model for a splendid array of topics such as the GIT that is its major organ, and the digestive system in overall (Litten-Brown, Corson & Clarke 2010).

To assess the appropriateness of porcine model, systematic comparison between the gut microflora of pigs and human is a must-do. In the following review, similarities and differences of the GIT in both anatomical and physical aspects between the two species are being concisely described, followed by a brief overview of their gut microbiota community and metabolic activities.

2.10.1. Similarities and Differences between the GIT and Body Constitution Of Pig and Human

Anatomically and physiologically, the porcine GIT is very similar to the human GIT (Roura 2016). Furthermore, its functionality, such as nutrient absorption by digestion and processing of metabolites through the gut bacterial metabolism, is highly similar to that of human (Litten-Brown, Corson & Clarke 2010). Moreover, another similarity is regarding the daily minimum nutrient requirements between the two species, which is indicated as a kilogram of dietary dry matter (Kuzmuk & Schook 2011; Lamarco 2012). And also, there is a comparable result of the intestinal length (0 – 1 m per kg of body weight) between them when the association between the length of intestines and body weight is calculated (Roura 2016).

Conversely, pigs and human have a difference in total length of GIT. When human becomes mature (around 33 yrs), the length of small intestine is 5.5 – 7 m and 1.5 m for the large intestine, but 15 – 22 m (small intestine) and 4 – 6 m (large intestine) for pigs when in the age of 3 yrs (Kuzmuk & Schook 2011). Another difference is that human has a distinct arrangement of the small and large intestine in their abdomen (Roura 2016), and each compartment of the small intestine clearly separated (Lamarco 2012).

Attention should also be paid to the quick growth performance and the size of new breed pigs in order to obtain the optimal comparison outcomes. Regarding body size, mini-/ grower pig is the best option as they have body weight gain of 70 – 120 kg at the adult stage, which is very comparable to human (Roura 2016). Besides, this pig contributes to a better/easier handling during studies.

2.10.2. Gut Microbiome of Pig and Human – Its Fermentation and Composition

Pig and human both are colonic fermenters, and have a similar gut microbiota composition (Miller & Ullrey 1987). However, microorganisms that form symbiotic associations inside the

intestines play only a minimal part in the DN nutrient synthesis (e.g. fatty acids and proteins)) compared to ruminants (Guilloteau et al. 2010). Pigs demonstrate a considerable fermentation in the caecum, and may receive almost 30% of its energy required for maintenance from microbially-produced SCFA by colonic fermentation (Ehle 1982). In contrast, humans show no a prominent caecum (Rerat 1987), and approximately 7% only of energy required for maintenance obtained from SCFA produced by the gut bacteria (Engelhardt 1997; Litten-Brown, Corson & Clarke 2010).

In the colon, the main metabolites produced by caecal fermentation include SCFA and gases, such as CO₂ and H₂ (Macfarlane & Macfarlane 2002). The biggest elements of SCFA are butyrate, propionate and acetate, and acetate is most distinct accounting for two-thirds of the total SCFA. While acetate is produced largely by diverse groups of microbes, butyrate and propionate (that widely known as the health-essential contributors for the host) are produced by only a limited group of gut bacteria (Macfarlane & Macfarlane 2002). For instance, propionate is metabolized extensively in liver and used for inhibiting lipogenesis as well as being a precursor for gluconeogenesis therein, whilst butyrate serves as the best source of energy for epithelial cells in the colon (Aimutis 2014). Typical producers of butyrate in the gut are clostridia including *Eubacterium rectale* and *Roseburia* spp (Engelhardt 1997).

The composition of microorganisms harboured in the gut of pig is similar to that found in human. Those gut microbes majorly comprise of Bacteroidetes phyla and Firmicutes. The major groups of bacteria in the GIT of pig consist of bacteria including *Butyrivibrio* spp., *Bifidobacterium* spp., *Lactobacillus* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *Ruminococcus* spp., *Clostridium* spp., *Eubacterium* spp., *Peptostreptococcus* spp., *Bacteroides* spp., *Escherichia* spp., and *Prevotella* (Frese et al. 2015). Holman et al. (2017) just collected the fecal samples five times in three-week intervals starting from 10 weeks of age, to do an assessment of the gut microbiome in pig. Results found two most plentiful microbial genera present in pigs, and those are *Prevotella* spp. – member of the *bacteroidetes phylum*, and *Anaerobacter* – belongs to the Firmicutes, amounting to 11.6% and 10.4% of the total microbiota, respectively. Interestingly, the abundance of the two genera oppositely changes (the former declines, and the latter increases) with the animals' age (Holman et al. 2017)

Basically, the gut microflora composition is dependent to a range of exogenous determinants (Isaccson & Kim 2012; Frese et al. 2015). Sanitary conditions and coprophagy, surrounding environment, age and diets/nutrition is the key contributing factors (Frese et al. 2015). For example, the microbial community of the GIT of pig is very adaptive to the dietary changes, as has been investigated the effects of feeding the pigs on different experimental diets by Susick et al. (2012); correspondingly, animal's diet can also affect the distribution of microbes in the colon of pig as for lactobacilli, found by Toth et al. (2015).

In short, the porcine model is the most appropriate translational model for testing dietary/nutritional inventions due to its very similar eating patterns, physiology of the GIT and greater size and gut microbiota compositions and their functions.

CHAPTER 3. PURPOSES OF THE RESEARCH

Hypothesis: Cholesterol in the plasma samples of pigs would be reduced when pigs are fed on diets containing polyphenol and dietary fibre rich black carrots.

Aim: This research aims to investigate the effects of polyphenol and dietary fiber rich black carrots after consumption on the reduction of total concentrations of plasma cholesterol.

Therefore, objectives of this study include: 1.) to compare weight gain of grower pigs fed either on low-fat (5%) or high-fat (15%) basal diet with added puréed or raw-diced black carrot against the control groups; 2.) to measure means particle size of diets changed in different digestive compartments; 3.) to analyze total plasma cholesterol concentrations of pigs fed on each diet treatment.

CHAPTER 4. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGIES

This study conducted the retrospective analyzes of previously collected samples from a comprehensive pig feeding experiment undertaken in mid- to the end of 2015. All experimental protocols were performed under approval by the Animal Ethics Committee of the University of Melbourne (approval 1413364.1). The following is brief history of the feeding study.

4.1. History of Pigs and Housing

The Aussie Pride Pork, located in Shepparton, Victoria, supplied all 40 pigs used in the entire feeding study. More details of the pig subjects were summarized in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Information of the Pig Subjects

Type/Species	Breed/Strain	Sex	Age	Total Number	Source
Pigs	Large White x Landrace 50kg	M	Grower	40	The Aussie Pride Pork

Note: M = Male

The pigs were housed in separated pens together with free movement space and good discharge system. In short, pens were commercial standard.

4.2. The Experimental Design

The whole feeding study consisted of 03 different stages, timeframes and with 02 collection points of samples (**Fig. 8**). Total duration of the study was 07 weeks.

FIGURE 8. The outlook over the whole experimental design. Initially, the 40 pigs were acclimatized for a week, followed by other 2-week time for inducing hypercholesterolemia with high fat diet. End point of that stage was regarded as *baseline* for the black carrot experiment where only blood samples collected once. Then, black carrot experiment started where the 40 pigs were divided into 06 different groups, including 16 pigs for LF and HF CONTROL, 12 pigs for LF and HF PUREED and 12 pigs for LF and HF RAW-DICED black carrot treatments, equally and respectively. This stage took 4-week time to *the end*, and another blood samples were collected together with collection of stomach, tract and faecal sample on the day of slaughtering.

With this comprehensive feeding experiment, there were 03 main tests aimed to be investigated, and they included as follows:

Test 1: To compare the effects of fat content added into the diets on the growth performance of the pig subjects. The feed formulations were used as described by Boyd & Mccracken (2014), and the ingredient composition of the diets is displayed in **Table 6**. Dietary energy intake was restricted to by 85% of the subjects' everyday requirement, to ensure complete diet consumption.

Test 2: To compare the effects of diets with versus without black carrot fibers. The recommended dietary intake of vegetables for Australian adults is 5 serves a day where 1 serve = ½ cup of cooked green/orange veggies such as broccoli or carrots, 1 serve = ½ of legumes or 1 cup of leafy salad greens. As for pigs, their energy intake requirement is ~ threefold higher than that for men, therefore pigs were given 7.5 cups of black carrot daily.

Table 6. Composition of the low-fat (5% fat) and high-fat (15% fat) basal diets*, <i>Source: Boyd & Mccracken (2014)</i>		
Ingredient	Low-fat diet (% dry mass)	High-fat diet (% dry mass)
Total fat	5.00	15.00
Wheat (11% crude protein)	78.40	61.64
Soyabean meal (48% crude protein)	7.82	14.29
Meat and bone meal (50% crude protein)	7.50	7.50
Blood meal (85% crude protein)	2.50	2.50
Tallow	1.60	8.40
Sunflower oil	0.80	4.20
Dicalcium phosphate	0.72	0.72
Salt	0.20	0.20
Vitamin-mineral premix	0.20	0.20
Lysine	0.15	0.15
Methionine	0.07	0.10
Threonine	0.00	0.05
Tylan	0.04	0.04
Fatty acids (% of total fatty acids)		
SFA	21.8	26.0
MUFA	27.3	29.3
PUFA	50.9	44.7
* Feed was adjusted weekly according to energy intake per weight of pigs: 14.6 MJ/kg for those on the basal diet containing 5% fat and 16.9 MJ/kg for those on the basal diet containing 15% fat.		

Source: Boyd & Mccracken (2014)

Test 3: To compare the effects of preparation methods, i.e. puréed versus raw diced black carrots. Thus, to accurately assess the effects of pureeing on the bioavailability of polyphenols, 2 cm-sized black carrot cubes were boiled (100°C) for 5 min, and followed by 4 min blending at high speed to achieve uniform particle size (PSD 575~700 µm). And, raw diced cubes of black carrots had size ~2 cm. A decision to use the raw diced black carrots was to ensure the difference between the puree and the raw black carrots because if the raw carrot cubes were cooked the texture would be soften, thereby no indication of difference between the two.

4.3. Feeding

The diets used to feed the pigs were based on a Western style human diet, which is made of 47% carbohydrates, 35% fat and 18% protein (Carré et al. 2002). The subjects were restricted to 30 MJ/day (~90% of their common energy intake), and this was to ensure the complete consumption of the diet. Therefore, the pigs were fed twice per day in the morning and in the afternoon, 40% and 60% respectively. Doses of experimental black carrots (see in **Fig. 8**) were added into the two meals for the subjects.

4.4. Sample Collection

There were two times (at 9 am and at 3 pm) of monitoring the test pigs for signs of illness. Their feed intake was daily recorded at a consistent time on a daily basis. Body weight gains were recorded at the start of the black carrots experiment (baseline) and weekly thereon (week 1, 2, 3 and 4). Because of their small weight, approximately 20 kg, the pigs were restrained with a snout rope to get jugular blood sample at baseline and at the end of the black carrot study. Blood samples were collected through the needles (size: 18G x 1.5 inch), kept in 16 x 100 ml tubes inside the 9.5 ml draw; via a VACUTAINER (Brand SST) and the process took less than two minutes. Immediately the whole blood samples were stored in freezer (-20°C) for future analysis.

Upon the completion of the feeding study, the pigs weighted 90 kg+, which was the appropriate size for slaughtering, at Diamond Valley Pork Processors. Portions of stomach, small intestine (jejunum and ileum), digestive tract and faecal samples were harvested at the abattoir and were immediately held in -20°C freezer awaiting further assessment (**Table 7**).

Table 7. Types, numbers and storage of samples collected during and after study

Sample/Description	Numbers of sample	Storage condition
Background diets*	80 packs	-20°C
LF diet + pureed black carrot	1 pack	
LF diet + raw diced black carrot	1 pack	
HF diet + pureed black carrot	1 pack	
HF diet + raw diced black carrot	1 pack	
Stomach	80 tubes	
Jejunum	80 tubes	
Ileum	80 tubes	
Ascending Colon	80 tubes	
Transverse Colon	80 tubes	
Descending Colon	80 tubes	
Feces	40 packs	
Baseline Blood Sample	40 tubes	
Blood Sample after experiment	40 tubes	

* Refer to both background LF and HF diets (i.e. not containing neither pureed nor raw diced black carrots)

4.5. The Current Study: Material and Methods

Washing out from the history of the comprehensive feeding study, this new study used and analyzed the samples collected in the past feeding study (see in **Table 7**).

4.5.1. Material

Deionized water (dH2O) and Ultrapure (Milli-Q) water was provided in the Chemistry and Microbiology laboratory (G23). Detergent solution to clean the cell surface of Malvern

Mastersizer 3000 was available in the Analysis laboratory at the School of Chemical and Biomolecular engineering. All chemicals used in the research were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific for the cholesterol assay include Amplex® Red reagent, MW= 257 (Component A), Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), anhydrous (Component B), Horseradish peroxidase (HRP) (Component C), Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), MW= 34 (Component D, 500 µL of a stabilized ~3% solution), 5X Reaction Buffer (Component E, 20 mL of 0.5 M potassium phosphate, pH 7.4, 0.25 M NaCl, 25 mM cholic acid, 0.5% Triton® X-100), Cholesterol oxidase, from Streptomyces (Component F), Cholesterol esterase, from Pseudomonas (Component G), Cholesterol reference standard, MW= 387 (Component H), Resorufin, sodium salt, MW= 235 (Component I).

4.5.2. Equipment

Corning® Clear Bottom 96-well plates (Catalog No. 3367, well volume: 360 µL, well depth: 11.3 mm, well diameter 6.86 mm, plate length 127.8 mm), FLUOstar Optima Microplate Reader (BMG LABTECH, Durham, NC), personal vortex mixer with silicon cup (200-2700 RPM, Model No. VM1-FT), and ductless fume cupboard (The SafeGuardPro™ 1800) were provided in the Plant Pathology Laboratory and Chemistry and Microbiology Laboratory, Faculty of Veterinary and Agricultural Sciences (FVAS), The University of Melbourne. Malvern Mastersizer 3000™ Laser particle size analyzer (ATA Scientific., UK) was hired for analysis in the Analysis laboratory at the School of Chemical and Biomolecular engineering. Automated wet dispersion unit/ Hydro EV (i.e. consists of 316 stainless, Borosilicate glass, Tygon®, FKM, PTFE, PEEK, Titanium Nitride).

4.5.3. Methods

This study consisted of three major analyzing parameters (**Table 8**).

Table 8. Analysis Scheme of this new study

Parameters	Analyzing Parameters		
	<i>A. Weight Gain (on a weekly basis)</i>	<i>B. Diet Particle Size</i>	<i>C. Total Concentrations of Plasma Cholesterol</i>
Methods			
Analysis Methods	Manual Records (Based on recorded weights in RECORD SHEET used during the feeding study)	Malvern Mastersizer 3000™ Laser particle size analyzer	Amplex® Red Cholesterol Assay kit, measuring under BMG Labtech FLUOstar Optima Microplate Reader

A. Body Weight of the Pigs

Weight of pigs was measured and recorded on a weekly basis throughout the past feeding study period. The every pig was weighted by guiding to the weighting scale. This weighting process

was performed before feeding on the day of each black carrot experimental week (refers to body weight record sheet in Appendix I).

B. Measurement of Diet Particle size - Sample Preparation

All samples, excepted blood sample listed in **Table 7** were used for diet particle size measurement. The sample preparation process prior to the measurement was depicted in **Fig. 9**.

FIGURE 9. Diagram of Sample Preparation for Diet Particle Size Measurement

- Sample Dispersion

Prior to the diet particle size measurement, sample dispersion is a must. This is to ensure the correct concentration and an appropriate, stable state of dispersed particles that are transported to the measurement area of the optical bench, thereby producing accurate and reliable measurement of the particle size. This process is controlled by a beam of the automated wet dispersion units (**Fig. 10**).

FIGURE 10. Hydro EV – automated wet dispersion unit

First, centrifuged sample suspension was manually blended before placing into the automated wet dispersion unit. Fraction of samples to be added in the unit was based on obscuration limit (Coarse particle, lower/upper limit= 10 – 20%).

- Laser Diffraction

After the sample was adequately dispersed or in a stable state of dispersion, it was transported to a laser diffraction measurement unit where a beam of laser moved through the dispersed particulate sample. As a result, the angular variation in the scattered light intensity was measured. Basically there was a contradiction in the way of scattering light between large and small particle, at small angles and at large angle relative the laser beam, respectively (**Fig. 11**) (Cools et al. 2014). Then the angular scattering intensity was analyzed to calculate the size of those particles via the use of the Mie theory of light scattering (Cools et al. 2014). The size of diet particles was reported as a volume equivalent sphere diameter.

FIGURE 11. Angular light scattering patterns of large and small particle
Source: Cools et al. (2014)

To achieve a precision of measurement, several tests were run to get an optimal setting for the Mastersizer. The overall optimal settings that were determined were only for the use of the manual measurement – hydro EV.

Instrument Setting:

Particle Type:	Non-spherical	Refractive index:	1.56
Absorption index:	0.1	Density (g/cm ³):	1.05
Dispersant refractive index:	1.33	Measuring duration (sec.):	30
Sequence of measurement:	Triplicates	Measuring delay (sec.):	10
Obscuration:	Coarse	Lower/Upper Limit:	10%/20%
Result type:	Volume distribution	Cleaning cycle:	3 times

- Measurement

Diet particle sizes were measured via Malvern Mastersizer 3000™ Laser particle size analyzer (ATA Scientific, Australia), which can detect particle between 0.01 and 3500 μm. 10% - 20% (lower/upper limit) of sample was added in a stirred tank filled with deionized water. The diluted sample was pumped into the measuring cell. The volumetric PSD were calculated from the scattered light with the Mie theory (as described in **Laser Diffraction**) by use the instrument’s software. Parameters D [v, 0.1], D [v, 0.5] and D [v, 09] (μm) indicate particle diameter at which 10, 50 and 90 volume (%) of the particles have a smaller diameter, respectively. For each sample, also the volume-based (D [4,3]) and the area-based (D [3,2]) diameter (μm) were determined based on the equations:

$$D[4,3] = \frac{\sum_i n_i d_i^4}{\sum_i n_i d_i^3}$$

$$D[3,2] = \frac{\sum_i n_i d_i^3}{\sum_i n_i d_i^2}$$

Where n_i is the number of particles of diameters d_i (μm). All analyzes were carried automatically by the instrument’ software in triplicate.

C. Analysis of the Total Plasma Cholesterol Concentrations

Cholesterol plays a key role in the organization and the function of eukaryotic cell membrane. While the cholesterol is variably distributed between the membranes of cells, it is enhanced in the plasma membrane. Some methods have been used for measuring the total concentrations of cholesterol in cells, e.g. Amplex® red cholesterol assay. Otherwise, in this research, the concentrations of plasma cholesterol were determined using the Amplex® red cholesterol assay kits and standards supplied by Thermo Fisher Scientific (Oregon, USA).

- Standard Curve for the Cholesterol Concentrations

The concentrations of standard solution were ready made by following the standard protocol provided by Thermo Fisher Scientific (Oregon, USA). Cholesterol concentrations of 0 - 8 μg/mL

were produced by first diluting 4 μL of the Cholesterol Reference Standard into 996 μL of 1X reaction buffer working solution to get a total volume of 1000 μL of the cholesterol concentration of 8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. From this highest standard concentration, other 10 cholesterol concentrations (7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2.5, 2, 1.5, 1, and 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were also made (**Table 9**). Also, 1X reaction buffer per se (without cholesterol) were used as a negative control.

- Sample Preparation

The fluorometric assays required 50 μL of sample for each reaction (well). Based on the results from the standard curve for the cholesterol concentrations, to analyze the total concentrations of plasma cholesterol, each blood sample required for a 1:200 dilution, where 400 μL of 1X reaction buffer was mixed with 2 μL of the plasma sample in a microcentrifuge tube.

Table 9. Protocol of Standard Cholesterol Concentrations			
<i>Standard Cholesterol Concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)</i>	<i>Volume of the Cholesterol Reference Standard (μL)</i>	<i>Volume of 1X Reaction Buffer (μL)</i>	<i>Total Volume (μL)</i>
Blank	0	0	0
0.5	10	150	160
1	20	140	160
1.5	30	130	160
2	40	120	160
2.5	50	110	160
3	60	100	160
4	80	80	160
5	100	60	160
6	120	40	160
7	140	20	160
8	4	996	1000

A positive control was prepared by diluting the 20 mM H_2O_2 working solution 10 μM in 1X reaction buffer. A working solution of 300 μM Amplex® red reagent containing 0.2 U/mL cholesterol esterase, 2 U/mL cholesterol oxidase, and 2 U/mL HRP was also made by the combined addition of 75 μL of Amplex® red reagent stock solution, 5 μL of the cholesterol esterase stock solution, 50 μL of the cholesterol oxidase stock solution, and 50 μL of HRP stock solution into 4.82 mL of 1X reaction buffer.

- Reaction

The reaction was begun by adding a volume of 50 μL diluted plasma sample with 50 μL of the working solution of 300 μM Amplex® red reagent containing 0.2 U/mL cholesterol esterase, 2 U/mL cholesterol oxidase, and 2 U/mL HRP into each microplate well. Then the reaction was incubated at 37°C for 60 min. The relative fluorescence was measured via FLUOstar Optima

Microplate Reader (BMG LABTECH, Durham, NC) with optimal settings below.

Measurement Type:	Fluorescence intensity (Top)
Flashes per well:	10
Reading Mode:	Endpoint
Multichromatic	
Excitation wavelength:	530-560 nm
Emission wavelength:	590 nm
Gain:	1000
Positioning delay:	0.2 seconds

- Calculation of the Concentration of Cholesterol

$$\text{Concentration of Cholesterol} = (S_a/S_v) \times Df^*$$

Where: S_a = Amount of cholesterol in unknown sample (μg) from standard curve
 S_v = Sample volume (μL) added into the wells
 C = Concentration of cholesterol in sample
 Df^* = The dilution factor will be 201 due to the 1:200 dilution with the 1X Reaction buffer.
Cholesterol molecular weight: 386.65 g/mole.

4.6. Statistical Analysis

Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied for testing interactions between treatments, followed by the fisher's least significant difference (LSD) comparisons test were used in statistical data analysis. Minitab (version 17.0) software was applied. Results were expressed as means and error bars of standard deviation, together with alphabetical letters (a, b, c) showing where significant difference existed. Significant difference was defined, as $p < 0.05$.

CHAPTER 5. RESULTS

5.1. Weight Gain Performance

As described in the **Fig. 8**, there was a four-week time for the black carrot experiment conducted after inducing cholesterolemia, but unfortunately, the fourth week's data was misplaced at the end of the feeding study. Thus, the results of weight gain in pigs fed on the six different diet treatments presented here are of the three weeks' duration data subtracting the baseline. Figure 12 depicted a quite similar upward trend in weekly means weight gain of pigs fed on all diet treatments both diet groups over the three-week period.

FIGURE 12. The comparison of means weight gain (kg) on a weekly basis in pigs fed on LFD (A) and HFD (B) diets that were added with either puréed or raw-diced black carrot, against each control treatment. The bar charts represent weekly means weight gain together with error bars of Stand. Deviation. Letters (a, b, c) were used as an indicator for any statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between data accordingly. $p > 0.05$ indicates no significant difference existed.

No indication of interactions neither between the LFD vs. HFD, and puréed vs. raw-diced) nor between diet groups vs. black carrot treatments (which all had the $p > 0.05$) was shown. However, regarding the LFD group, mean weight gain in pigs fed in supplementation with raw-diced black carrot were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the other two for the first two weeks. In contrast, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the control and the LFD with puréed black carrot added for the three-week time. For the HFD group, in the period of three weeks with inclusion of black carrot experiment, the three diet treatments namely the HFD- control, puréed and raw-diced black carrot showed no any significant difference in means weight gain at all ($p > 0.05$).

However, despite no indication of statistically significant difference in weight gain of pigs fed on diets with puréed and raw-diced black carrot treatment, regardless the fat levels of the diets, **Fig. 12** displayed that almost all pigs in the HFD group had quite lower weight gain compared to those in the LFD group.

In addition, it is worth noting that the difference in fat content in dietary treatments had no effect on the weight gain in pigs ($p > 0.05$). In overall, as shown by the means weight gain in **Fig. 12**, it almost had the same trend that all diet treatments of the two diet groups once in the presence of

black carrot, both puréed or raw-diced incorporated, the increasing levels of weight gain were relatively lower than the control treatments.

5.2. Particle Size of Dietary Treatment

Particle size analysis indicated a significant reduction in size of the diet particles, where were passing through digestive compartments in each pig, on the day of slaughtering.

FIGURE 13. Change in means PSD (μm) passed through each digestion part in pigs of the three dietary treatments in the low fat diet group. LFD = Low Fat Diet, B.C = Black Carrot. [~ 2 cm] posted before the LFD-RAW-DICED B.C was to inform that the raw particle size of that treatment could not be measured by the Mastersizer, but by basing on the size of carrot cube once diced. Letters (a, b, c) were used as an indicator for any statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). For standard deviation refers to Appendix III.

FIGURE 14. Change in PSD (μm) passed through each digestion part in pigs of the three dietary treatments in the high fat diet group. HFD = How Fat Diet, B.C = Black Carrot. [~ 2 cm] posted before the HFD-RAW-DICED B.C was to inform that the raw particle size of that treatment could not be measured by the Mastersizer, but by basing on the size of carrot cube once diced. Letters (a, b, c) were used as an indicator for any statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). For standard deviation refers to Appendix III.

Raw particle sizes of the LFD-CONTROL and LFD-PURÉED B.C were 658 and 707 μm (**Fig. 13**), respectively while these were significantly lower than those in the HFD, which were 689.33 and 786.33 μm , respectively (**Fig. 14**). However, for the two diet groups, the treatment of raw-diced B.C cannot be measured via the instrument due to its greater cube, and consequently,

their raw sizes were determined based on real size of the cube when dicing (~2 cm). Moreover, difference ($p < 0.05$) in sizes of raw particles of diet treatments resulted in a significant difference in the reduced amounts of particle size from being digested inside the stomach until becoming faeces. This happened identically in both diet groups.

All the particle sizes of diet treatments in the HFD were all statistically significantly higher than those in the LFD at the $p < 0.05$. Besides, an overall picture of the reduction in particle size of the diets (**Fig. 13 & Fig. 14**) was that in a logical order, which RAW-DICED B.C treatment, had an immeasurable raw particle size but largest when reaching stomach, and remained the largest, followed by the PURÉED B.C and the CONTROL treatment accordingly.

Table 10 displayed the summarized results of reduced means amount of particle size (μm) of all diet treatments in both LFD and HFD group, which were obtained from subtraction of means PSD (μm) in every next digestive compartment to each previous compartment (i.e. means PSD in stomach – means PSD of raw particle size, and Ileum – Jejunum and so on).

Table 10. Amount of PSD (μm) of diet treatments reduced from each stage of digestion						
Diet Type \ Stage of Digestion	LOW FAT DIET			HIGH FAT DIET		
	<i>LFD-CONTROL</i>	<i>LFD-PURÉED B.C</i>	<i>LFD-RAW-DICED B.C</i>	<i>HFD-CONTROL</i>	<i>HFD-PURÉED B.C</i>	<i>HFD-RAW-DICED B.C</i>
Raw particle size	658	707	~2 cm	689.33	786.33	~2 cm
Stomach	43.67	46	776.58	53.76	96.92	856.37
Jejunum	51.33	51	79.25	55.15	54.41	78.97
Ileum	103.17	74.17	81.73	77.21	85.97	106.15
Ascending colon	12.42	69.92	132.5	18.57	53.2	140.35
Transverse colon	24.51	26.75	18.6	36.93	14.17	25.5
Descending colon	7.9	78.25	79.75	69.5	85.5	94.9
Faces	204	103.08	92.09	143.07	114.5	104.3

Note: LFD = Low Fat Diet; HFD = High Fat Diet; B.C = Black Carrot

However, there was an exception in both LFD- and HFD-RAW DICED B.C treatment (highlighted in dark-purple color) that the amount of PSD reduced from raw size to stomach was unknown. Results showed the sizes of diets' particle that reduced from all digestive compartments inside the stomach and small intestine, namely jejunum and ileum were relatively comparable (i.e. 198.17, 171.17 and 160.98 μm , for LFD- CONTROL, PURÉED and RAW DICED B.C, respectively, and 186.12, 237.3 and 185.12 μm , for HFD- CONTROL, PURÉED and RAW-DICED B.C, respectively) to the reduced amounts of particle size inside the large intestine from ascending colon downing to feces, which were 236.41, 208.08 and 190.44 μm , for LFD- CONTROL, PURÉED and RAW DICED B.C, respectively, and 249.5, 214.17 and 224.7 μm , for HFD- CONTROL, PURÉED and RAW-DICED B.C, respectively.

Furthermore, by comparison between the reduced amounts of means particle size of each diet treatment in both diet groups (LFD, HFD) in the small intestine and that in the large intestine, the amounts of means particle size of the RAW-DICED B.C's diet treatments were reduced in the lowest rate (i.e. the reduced PSD of both LFD- and HFD-RAW-DICED B.C < LFD- and HFD-PURÉED B.C < LFD- and HFD-CONTROL). Also, it is quite important to note that the largest amounts of diets' particle size across the six diet treatments were reduced in the ileum, which is the third and final part of the small intestine while in the descending colon, which is a segment of the large intestine.

In short, there was a significant reduction in particle size of all the six diet treatments after consumption. The similar amounts of particle size of diets reduced occurred in both the small and large intestine for the both diet groups. And, all diet treatments with either raw-diced or puréed black carrot added had lower reduced amounts of means particle size in both the small and the large intestine compared to the control groups.

5.3. Total Concentrations of Plasma Cholesterol

The standard curve of the 12 cholesterol conentrations including blank is presented in **Fig. 15** just below. As seen from the plot, the cholesterol concentrations were selected at the range from 0.5 µg/mL to 6.0 µg/mL at the incubation time of 60 minutes and pH = 7.4, because as at the concentrations of 7.0 and 8.0 µg/mL the reading value of fluorecence in relative fluorecence units (RFU) appeared stable and fell. Otherwise, the equation of linear fit ($y= 236.97x$) was generated from the standard curve across the selected range of standard concentrations (**Fig. 16**) with $R^2= 0.98$.

FIGURE 15. The cholesterol standard curve obtained from the measurement using the FLUOstar Optima Microplate Reader (BMG LABTECH, Durham, NC) (incubation time = 60 min, temperature: 37°C, pH = 7.4). RFU = Relative Fluorescence Units.

FIGURE 16. The linear fit of the first 10 standard concentrations: 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 4, 5, and 6 with the set intercept = 0.

FIGURE 17. Total concentrations of plasma cholesterol in pigs from all dietary treatments of the LFD group (A) and the HFD group (B). The barcharts displayed with MEANS \pm Stand. Deviation. Letters (a, b, c) were used as an indicator for any statistically significant difference. $p > 0.05$ shows no significant difference existed.

There was no an interaction between diets and black carrots added ($p = 0.98$). In LFD group, pigs fed on the control treatment had the highest total cholesterol concentrations in plasma (482 ± 3.21 mg/dL) while the lowest concentration (342 ± 2.76 mg/dL) belonged to those fed LFD with added raw-diced black carrot (**Fig. 17A**). Anyway, no statistically significantly differences ($p > 0.05$) were indicated between the three dietary treatments within the LFD group.

Similarly, in the HFD, the means total concentrations of plasma cholesterol were not significant different ($p > 0.05$) between pigs that fed on the control, HFD with added puréed or raw-diced black carrot treatment. Besides, the same pattern happened, where the control treatment got the highest total concentrations of plasma lipid (583 ± 5.02 mg/dL), followed by the HFD+ puréed (462 ± 4.20 mg/dL) and finally the HFD+ raw-diced black carrot (386 ± 2.95 mg/dL) as shown in **Fig. 17B**.

Moreover, in comparison of the total plasma cholesterol concentrations (mg/dL) in pigs fed on LFD with those fed on HFD, there was also no indication of significant difference between the two at $p > 0.05$. In overall, from the result shown herein, there appears to have a positive health contribution in terms of getting lower total concentrations of plasma lipid when black carrots were incorporated into either low fat- or high fat diet, despite no significant difference from the control treatment.

CHAPTER 6. DISCUSSION

Weight gain – dietary fiber: The weight gains for pigs fed either on low fat or high fat diets with inclusion of black carrots, which are a main polyphenol-rich dietary fiber vegetable), in different processed formats (pureed or raw diced) were relatively lower than those obtained for pigs fed on the control diets. As such, these findings were in agreement with observations of Slavin (2005), whose research was conducted to assess the effects of dietary fiber rich diets on body weight. And, results from that research pointed out an inverse relationship between intake of dietary fiber and body weight changing. Also, Pereira (2008) supported this result in a study with 252 participants, who were all women in their middle age. For a 20-month period of time, it was found that all middle-aged women lost weight in an average of 2 kg when increasing dietary fiber to 8 g/1000 kcal. This change in weight was predominantly because of reduced body fat. At the same time, it ought to be acknowledged that the connection of dietary fiber and weigh loss was independent of various major determinants, which include age, baseline energy intake, activity level, and baseline fiber and fat intakes. Du et al. (2009) agreed with the aforementioned findings and suggest an association between dose and response. They reported the decreased body weight by 0.5 kg per every 40 g per day of increased intake of vegetable. Additionally, carrots appeared to be potential in decreasing weight gain by 0.36 kg per intake of 20 g a day.

The ability of dietary fiber to slow down weight gain may be attributable to some factors. Firstly, production of glucagon-like peptide and peptide YY occurs during caecal fermentation of soluble fiber (Lairon 2007). A major role of these two gut hormones is to induce satiety. Secondly, dietary fiber could essentially act on the reduction of energy intake (Adam et al. 2014). For instance, there was a declined trend in consumption of dietary fat amongst women who were offered with increased fiber intake. Thirdly, the fiber could also reduce a dietary metabolizable

energy (ME), which is a subtraction of the energy lost in the combustible gases, urine and feces from gross energy (Morenga, Mallard & Mann 2012). Similar observation by Guérin-Deremaux et al. (2013) found that a high intake of dietary fiber consumption constitutes a decreased dietary ME. This may contribute to the fact that digestibility of fat dwindled as dietary fiber increased. Moreover, the simple carbohydrate intake decreased as the intake of dietary fiber increased. The reason of this is despite the contribution of dietary fiber to the total dietary caloric content, dietary fiber is much more resistant to digestion in the upper- and somewhat even to the lower-tract (Lairon 2007).

Also, there should have a recognition that the inverse correlation between dietary fiber and ME was dietary-fat independent (Guérin-Deremaux et al. 2013). Thus, ME declined while dietary fiber enhanced in both LFD and HFD. On the other hand, when splitting dietary fiber into insoluble and soluble, the results became more questionable (Kamara, Kamara & Castonguay 1992). ME was increased when soluble fiber was added to a HFD, but reduced when added to a LFD (Guo 2009). This is consistent with the result of this current research that found weight gain in pigs fed HFD with added pureed black carrot, containing about 1.5 g soluble fiber, which is three-fold higher than raw-diced black carrot, in 114.35 g (Danzy & Landry 2013) was higher than those fed LFD group. However, influence of dietary fat on the effects of soluble fiber remains unknown. Wang et al. (2007) also reported supportive findings that mice put in more weight when inclusion of soluble fiber into a high fat diet. There are a few mechanisms that could elaborate how soluble fiber elevates weight gain/ME. First, the increase in populations of bacteria in the large intestine is a result of consumption of high soluble fiber intake (Lindberg 2014). Otherwise, this stimulates fermentation and utilization of SCFA resulting in enhanced absorption of energy. Second, in the GIT, soluble fiber expands and develops a viscous material causing a delay in the intestinal transit time (Yan et al. 2013), thereby allowing for more complete digestion and absorption. In contrast, others oppose that this increased viscosity has a negative impact and impedes absorption (Schrauwen & Saris 2006; Flatt 2010).

The effects of insoluble fiber are very likely to be contrasting from soluble fiber. Mice eating both a low fat and a high fat diet had its body weight decreased when increasing the intake of insoluble fiber added to the diets (Yue et al. 2017). Research in vegetables, such as carrots, and sows showed that digestibility of energy is decreased with the intake of insoluble fiber while increased with soluble fiber (Flis, Sobotka & Antoszkiewicz 2017). The underlying mode of action could be an increased passage rate through the GIT caused by insoluble fiber (Yue et al. 2017). This may be expected to diminish nutrient digestion and absorption.

According to the results in this study as well as the supportive data presented above, dietary fiber (both insoluble and soluble fiber) of black carrots may be a contributing factor to a lower weight gain in pigs. However, there appears to have a link between the diet types (low or high fat) and the fiber types eaten.

Weight gain – Anthocyanin: Moreover, the anthocyanins, naturally occurring flavonoid pigments present in large amount in black carrots, are also suggested to have beneficial effects on attenuating weight gain of pigs. In recent years, anthocyanins have been identified as a potential controller for lipid metabolism and energy uses via the reduction of body fat mass and improve lipid profiles *in-vivo* studies. In a study of Azzini, Giacometti & Russo (2017), black chokeberries (containing similar amount of anthocyanins compared to black carrots) juice

concentrate was added to a low fat diet and offered to pig. Results showed that the pigs fed on that diet gained lower body weights and had less epididymal fat than pigs fed on control diet (no juice concentrate added). They concluded that juice concentrate of black chokeberries has the body fat reduction potential under normal dietary condition (Azzini, Giacometti & Russo 2017).

In another study, Esposito et al. (2015) found that feeding pigs on a simple HFD significantly increased the size of fat cells of the pigs, but this effect did not appear in pigs that fed on a HFD with added anthocyanins extracted from purple corn. In addition, the HFD has been known to induce not only hypercholesterolemia but also hyperglycemia; however, the inclusion of purple corn anthocyanins into the diet reversed these effects. Their conclusion was that anthocyanins from fruit and vegetables are potential to decrease weight gain (Esposito et al. 2015).

Furthermore, the Queen Garnet plum that is anthocyanin-rich from Australia has been evaluated as a potential aid in weight loss. A research team led by professor Lindsay Brown, the University of Southern Queensland, observed that purple juice made from the plum reversed health problems related to obesity in rats that fed a HFD and a high carbohydrate diet (as cited in Santhakumar et al. 2015). The Queen Garnet plum contains 5 times more anthocyanins than that contains in common plum. This quantity is quite similar to that in black carrots, which has approximately 4 times higher than other purple vegetables (Algarra et al. 2014). As also discovered by Bhaswant et al. (2015; 2017), who treated obese rats eight weeks in age with anthocyanins from purple sweet potato, they figured out that compared to the control group, the rats treated with anthocyanins sourced from the potato lost more weight. This may indicate that the synergistic effect of anthocyanins and dietary fibers containing in black carrots exhibited a beneficial mechanism on attenuating weight gain (Poudyal, Panchal & Brown 2010).

The effects of cooking – Pureed vs. Raw-diced on weight gain: Weight gain results in this study demonstrated that pigs fed on both LFD and HFD with added pureed black carrot gained higher weight than pigs fed on the diets with added raw-diced black carrot, irrespective of fat content of the diets. The effects of heat processing applied in making puree of black carrots may be a reason for this difference. Currently, it becomes a general consensus that the effect of heat treatment on dietary fiber is very complicated (Takeyama, Fukushima & Tanimura 2002; Gonzalez-Alvarado et al. 2008; Bengtsson, Wikberg & Tornberg 2011). Marked differences have been found in raw material, not only between vegetables itself but also between various cultivars of the same vegetable (Takeyama, Fukushima & Tanimura 2002). Sreeramuluand and Raghunath (2010), who studied on the effects that processing has on dietary fiber in vegetables, found that boiling carrots reduced total content of dietary fiber. And, in some cases, there was a change in distribution of insoluble and soluble fiber. Zia-Ur-Rehman, Islam and Shah (2003) discovered that fiber content in raw carrots differs from that in cooked carrots. Cooking carrots allows the cells to hold on more water, thereby increasing the content of soluble fiber. In addition, Komolka and Górecka (2012) reported that cooking caused a significant reduction of hemicellulose content in carrots by 26.8%. Gonzalez-Alvarado et al. (2008) also reported that the physiochemical parameters and nutritional quality of vegetables (e.g. carrots, broccoli) are modified by common cooking practice. Heating may influence on the content of dietary fiber as well as alter the physiochemical attributes of dietary fiber, which in turn results in changing physiological activities of dietary fiber (Fabbri & Crosby 2016).

A part from the effects of cooking on dietary fiber content, stability of anthocyanins is also strongly affected by the degree and duration of heating. In Kırca, Özkan and Cemeroğlu (2007)' study, they found that the content of anthocyanins in elderberries was very susceptible to heating. At 95°C for three hours heating, only 50% of elderberries' anthocyanins content was retained. Processing blueberries into puree by blanching at 95°C for 3 min and followed by pasteurization destroyed 48% of the total monomeric anthocyanins content, compared to the original levels found in the fresh fruits (Sadilova, Carle & Stintzing 2007). In raspberry purees, similar amount of the lost pigment was also reported by Sarkis et al. (2013). Lee et al. (2013) reported that 10 – 80% of anthocyanins lost in jam processing when boiling for 5 – 10 min.

A combination of blanching, boiling and duration has a strong influence on anthocyanin content in fruit and vegetables. For instance, recently Cosme, Pinto and Vilela (2017) reported that cooking, blanching and steaming resulted in 59%, 41% and 29% losses, respectively in the content of anthocyanins of purple potato. Aamir et al. (2013) and Presilska (2016) reported the similar findings in blueberry and red cabbage respectively. Recently Rothwell et al. (2014) found that pelargonidin-3-glucoside and cyanin- din-3-glucoside in strawberry and blueberry puree were strongly affected by heating of 70°C for two minutes. Kırca, Özkan and Cemeroğlu (2017) just found that black carrot anthocyanins are stable at 70 - 80°C, and this is corresponding to the kinetic data by Garba et al. (2015) on thermal stability of anthocyanins from black carrots at 70 - 90°C. However, as reported by Albarici and Pessoa (2012), polyphenols of black carrot were completely lost after boiling, while frying and steaming destroyed its polyphenolic content of 31% and 43% respectively. So, as in this study, cubes of black carrot were boiled (100°C) during the holding time of 5 minutes, its anthocyanin pigments as well as dietary fiber may be destructed or retained at lower levels compared to that in the fresh raw-diced black carrots.

However, no significant difference in weight gain in terms of statistics between diet treatments of low fat diet group and those of high fat diet group was observed, and this appeared to be an unusual feature, but this may occur due to too short duration of the experiment. Boyd and Mccracken (2014) found that a diet containing 10% added fat helped increased weight gain and feed efficiency of pigs compared to 1.5% added fat diet for a eight-week period. Otherwise, further studies are needed here by extending the experimental duration in order to investigate if there would have an indication of significant difference between the two diet types. And, in this study, it appears to be greater potential to utilize black carrot for controlling the body weight gain regardless of fat levels, in ratios added into diets.

Particle size of diet - weight gain: The recommended particle size for use in pigs' diet is 700 – 800 µm (Vukmirović et al. 2017). And, Flis, Sobotka and Antoszkiewicz (2017) classified the swine diet particle size into three types including coarse (871 – 947 µm), medium (671 – 773 µm) and fine (536 – 574 µm). The analyzed results of all dietary treatments' particle size in this study indicated a significant difference between them. Despite this, based on the category of diet particle size, it was noted that the particle size of the control and pureed treatments of both HFD and LFD fall into the medium type, while it is undeterminable for the raw-diced treatments but must be much larger that can be considered a coarser diet.

Kim et al. (2002) reported that pigs fed on coarser diet gained less body weight and less feed efficiency compared to those fed on finer particle diet. This finding concurs the results of weight gain in pigs of this research, which showed that weight gain of: the control > the pureed > the

raw-diced treatment. There are two mechanisms including a delayed digesta transit time and the better nutrient digestibility caused by the larger particles that could explain this point. There is a hypothesis that quick passage rate results in a reduced time available for digestion and absorption (Stark & Chewning 2012). Guay et al. (2012) have proposed that larger diet particles are retained for longer time in the digestive tract than smaller particles such as medium, so it helps extend means residence time. Likewise, Maulfair, Fustini and Heinrichs (2011) suggested that coarse (larger) diet particles may slow down the digesta transit time through the stomach, thereby providing more time available for nutrients to expose to the digestive enzymes, which results in increasing the utilization of energy and digestibility of nutrients. Therefore, from these supportive data, the diets with added raw-diced black carrot (~2 cm in size) were the most beneficial treatment in terms of weight gain management.

In addition, another critical point highlighted the results of means quantity of reduced diet particle sizes was of that the diets with raw-diced black carrot treatment had the least reduced quantity of particles compared to the control diets and the diets with pureed black carrot treatment. This result corresponded to the finding of Arscott and Tanumihardjo (2010), who reported that black carrot dietary fibers are mostly non-digestible fibers. So, the particle size of that treatment remained larger. The results also revealed that there was a comparable reduction of diet particles of all dietary treatments during digesting in the small intestine to the size reduction in the large intestine. This result quite contradicted to a finding of Phillips et al. (2012) who reported that a larger amount of diet particles is reduced in the small intestine. Also, Newman et al. (2016) found that about 90% of nutrient processing and absorption is completed in the small intestine.

Fiber, particle size of diet and total concentrations of plasma cholesterol: Regarding the total cholesterol concentrations in plasma samples, the results from this current research revealed that pigs fed on the diets with added raw-diced black carrots, which were found containing high fiber content, bound anthocyanins and having larger particle size, had the lowest plasma cholesterol concentration. This was in agreement with Capuano (2016), who fed pigs on a normal high fat diet with 250 g/day of fiber inclusion for six weeks. Their finding indicated that total cholesterol in blood samples of the pigs was significantly lower than those of the control group (400 mg/dL vs. 768 mg/dL). Similarly, these results supported the previous studies that daily consumption of fresh black carrots in combination with a normal diet results in lower plasma cholesterol profile (Park et al. 2015; Park et al. 2016). However, the mechanism explaining on how total plasma cholesterol concentrations are reduced by fiber remains unclear. Pojer et al. (2013) give supportive evidence that dietary fiber may attach with bile acids and cholesterol during the intraluminal formation of micelle. Moreover, the resulting decrease of liver's cells cholesterol content stimulates an up-regulation of the low-density lipoprotein (LDL) receptor, and consequently increasing the LDL clearance. However, elevated excretion of bile acid is probably not enough to be account for the observed reduction of cholesterol concentration (Kahlon & Smith 2007). Other mechanisms have also been suggested including improved satiety that leads to lower overall energy intake (Clark & Slavin 2013), slowed absorption of macronutrients due to fibers with high viscosity that leads to an increased insulin sensitivity (Lattimer & Haub 2010), and changes in intestinal motility (Gonlachavit 2004).

At the same time, increasing research reports that the inhibition of fatty acid synthesis by the products of bacterial fermentation in the gut (production of SCFA such as acetate, butyrate and

propionate) has shown to lower plasma concentration of cholesterol in human, pig and rat (Jha & Berrocoso 2016). Synthesis of cholesterol is made through a complex metabolic pathway from the acetyl-CoA. In that pathway, 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA (HMGC) reductase is the rate-limiting enzyme (Holscher 2017). Evidence from *in-vitro* studies showed that propionate decreases the rate of cholesterol synthesis by reducing the activity of HMGC reductase and HMGC synthase (Fleming & Kobayashi 2001). Also, *in-vivo* studies, $^3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used as a tracer, and results showed decreased rate of total cholesterol synthesis in the livers of pigs and mice when adding propionate into their feeds. Acetate also has influence on plasma cholesterol profile, thus decreased hypercholesterolemia in human as observed by Yang, Keshavarzian and Rose (2013).

In response to the beneficial effects of SCFA on the reduced total plasma cholesterol levels, an interesting study of Vinolo et al. (2013) found that inclusion of dietary fiber, especially fermentable fiber into feed is very successful in improving the fermentation and the microbial composition in the gut. Non-digestible fiber, together with other food components, such as bound polyphenols will exit the small intestine and enter the large intestine where those dietary components are more totally digested (Bindelle et al. 2008), via the gut microbial fermentation. Therefore, raw-diced black carrots, which were added to the diets, were very likely to act as the major substrate for the gut microbes to ferment, producing certain beneficial SCFA.

Furthermore, this study found that diet treatments with larger particle size had lowest total concentrations of plasma cholesterol. And, this result is the same as a finding of Day et al. (2012). In fact, accessibility to the fibers by the gut microflora can be affected by the particle size, porosity and surface area characteristics of the fiber (Jenkins et al. 2011). Day et al. (2012) studied the fermentation kinetics of black carrot's cell wall particle dispersion with different particle size and measured SCFA produced at time intervals up to two days. Her results demonstrated that larger particles were fermented very quick, increased more production of SCFA. On the other hand, Moen et al. (2016) suggested that smaller particles as a key driver for more quick fermentation because of its greater specific surface areas.

Bound anthocyanins and lowered plasma cholesterol concentrations: A part from cholesterol lowering effects of raw-diced black carrots fibers, bound anthocyanins with black carrots' fibers may be another crucial contributing factor to decrease the concentrations of plasma cholesterol. As found in this research, pigs fed on all dietary treatments with black carrots had lower cholesterol level in blood. This result was in line with some other *in-vivo* experiments that have reported a marked decline in level of blood cholesterol after the consumption of anthocyanin-rich foods. For example, consuming grapes reduced total concentrations of plasma cholesterol to around 50% after 4 weeks (Mori et al. 2007), a cocoa beverage reduced to 15% after 2 months (Reis et al. 2016), and strawberries reduced to 31% after a month (Wallace 2013). The variation in reduction percentage is highly likely due to the different content of anthocyanins in each food materials (Mori et al. 2007). Day et al. (2012) suggests that anthocyanins bind to cell wall of vegetables, such as black carrots can be processed during digestion and absorbed into bloodstreams, leading to decreased lipid peroxidation within the plasma compartments. Besides, mechanistic studies figure out several other mechanisms of action which anthocyanins exert including inhibitory effects on increased cytokine production, estrogenic activities, inflammatory activities, membrane strengthening, reduced capillary permeability and fragility, enzyme

inhibition and DNA cleavage, and all these are strongly linked to cardiovascular disease protection.

Moreover, absorption and metabolism are the major determinants for biological activities of anthocyanins (Mcghie & Stevenson 2013). A current research has just found that in the stomach and intestine of pigs, the absorption of anthocyanins is very quick (Wiczkowski, Szawara-Nowak & Romaszko 2016). Anthocyanins in the stomach tissues of pigs were identified due to changes in their spectral changes at pH = 1, 4.5 and 10, yet HPLC cannot quantify that anthocyanin content as because they appear bound to unidentified material of food (Xiao et al. 2017). A study of Borges et al. (2007) reported that uptake of anthocyanins from black raspberry in the tissue of small intestine reached 7.5%, which was significantly greater than the reported uptake in plasma. Other *in-vivo* studies reported similar results of low uptake of anthocyanins in plasma such as 0.078 - 3.2% from cranberry (Mcghie & Stevenson 2013), 1.8 – 2% from strawberry (Tulipani et al. 2011). This implies that the intact anthocyanins are not efficiently transported into the circulation due to nonspecific or specific binding to the plant cell wall material or food matrix. These data may well elaborate the result of this study that although large amount of anthocyanins available in the raw-diced black carrots, their bioavailability may be low as they become bound to the cell wall of the carrots, leading to only decreased cholesterol level but not significant difference from the control groups. Additionally, the comparatively higher cholesterol levels in the pureed treatment may be due to the strong influence of cooking on fiber and anthocyanins content in black carrots. In addition, the degree of difference in anthocyanin bioavailability in circulation, especially plasma, can result from variation in xenobiotic metabolism in the GIT, liver and other tissues of living organisms (Kamiloglu et al. 2015).

As discussed above regarding black carrot dietary fiber, nondigestible fibers will be going to the large intestine with company of bound anthocyanins. The fibers serve as a key substrate for the gut microbiota to attach and ferment. At the same time, increasing recent studies report that gut microflora can release and metabolize the bound anthocyanins, producing more bioavailable and smaller SCFA via colonic fermentation (Mazza & Kay 2008; Bobrich et al. 2014). D'Archivio et al. (2010) conducted a mice experiment to investigate the microbial deglycosylation and degradation of six anthocyanins via use of HPLC. Results indicated that glycosides of anthocyanins in the study were hydrolyzed by gut bacteria into aglycons (or anthocyanidins). At pH=7, liberated aglycons are not stable, leading to pigment degradation. First, cy-3-rut was hydrolyzed into cy-3-glu, then into cyanidin aglycon that quickly degraded into 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid / protocatechuic acid as a product of gut microbiota of human (Ichianagi et al. 2006). Nitralova et al. (2012) used the porcine gut bacteria to metabolize anthocyanins from purple potato *in-vitro*. They found those bacteria metabolized the anthocyanins into various products, such as phenylbutyric acids, phenylpropionic acids, phenylacetic acid, gallic acid, phloroglucinol acid, phloroglucinol aldehyde, urolithin A and B, vanillic acid and syringic acid. Smaller phenolic acids and other metabolites of anthocyanins possess potential microbial stability and greater chemical, suggesting that they can be more absorbed into the plasma exerting the physiological effects and improving antioxidant activities as reported in numerous studies (Nardini et al. 2002; Campos & Markham 2007; Bresciani et al. 2017). From this perspective, the supplementation of raw-diced black carrots into diets seemed more effective in lowering total plasma cholesterol levels, and this is quite consistent with finding of this study.

CHAPTER 7. CONCLUSION & FUTURE STUDIES

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of polyphenol-rich dietary fiber found in black carrots on plasma cholesterol levels of pigs by comparing the weight gain and total concentrations of plasma cholesterol of pigs subjected to two diet types (low and high fat) coupled with supplementation of black carrots (pureed and raw-diced formats) for 28 days against the control groups. Measurement of diet particle size showed a significant difference between the means diet particle size of all diet treatments, indicating that when adding black carrots the diet particle became larger compared to the controls. Whereas, no significant difference existed between the mean weekly weight gain as well as the mean total plasma cholesterol concentrations of pigs fed on the diets with added black carrots and those without black carrot supplementation, irrespective of the fat levels of the diets. From a statistical perspective, the hypothesis that cholesterol in the plasma samples of pigs would be reduced when pigs are fed on diets containing polyphenol and dietary fibre rich black carrots was not supported. However, by observing the trends in weight gain and total cholesterol levels of plasma samples, there was a positive indication that the diets with added black carrots can contribute to minimal weight gain and also lowered total levels of plasma cholesterol. The possible underlying mechanisms that influence this trend would be the health-promoting effects of black carrot fibers and anthocyanins as in line with many studies. The effect of processing could be a causative factor in producing different results between pureed and raw-diced black carrot treatments. This study used and analyzed the past samples, which were collected last two years, so longevity of samples may affect the samples despite of freezing. Another limitation was due to the only one-time analysis of total concentrations of blood cholesterol. Perhaps this study could be improved by analyzing the total blood cholesterol levels in three replicates.

Further studies are required for the correlation between fiber structures of black carrots, such as morphology and particle size, and the fermentation. Specifically, it would be interesting to assess whether higher production of SCFA and faster rate of fiber fermentation from larger diet particles due to preferential attachment of microbial species or not. The impacts of processing on black carrots' state/structures as well as properties are very complex, so further investigations are needed to better understand this multivariate interaction. Also, additional determination of optimal fibers contents from black carrots for the purpose of weight and cholesterol control would be a good additional study.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix I. Weekly Body Weight Record During the Black Carrot Experiment

SPPL:	Veterinary & Agricultural Sciences (045)	ETHICS ID:	1413364.1		
AEC:	Faculty of Veterinary and Agricultural Sciences				
PROJECT SUPERVISOR & DEPARTMENT:	Prof Frank Dunshea Agriculture And Food Systems	PRIMARY CONTACT & DEPARTMENT:	Dr Anneline Padayachee Agriculture And Food Systems		
BODY WEIGHT RECORD SHEET					
PERFORMER AND REORDER:		Dr Anneline Padayachee Ashley Gabler Emma Klapish			
	Baseline	Week1	Week2	Week3	Week4
Pen/Pig	28/9/15	5-Oct	12/10/15	19/10/15	26/10/15
1	76.5	84.5	90.5	101	
2	71	78.5	86	90	
3	61.5	70.5	78.5	85.5	
4	72	83	90	98.5	
5	68.5	78.5	85	93.5	
6	66	73.5	78	87	
7	74.5	81.5	86	96	
8	74	84	90	91.5	
9	69.5	78	84	86	
10	66.5	74.5	82	82.5	
11	68.5	76.5	81.5	86	
12	63	72.5	81.5	88	
13	64.5	73	80	87	
14	76	84.5	91	98	
15	73	82.5	90	100.5	
16	76.5	85	92.5	99.5	
17	63	70.5	75.5	83	
18	74.5	81	87.5	95.5	
19	71	80.5	86.5	94.5	
20	76	81.5	94	102	
21	74.5	83	90	96.5	
22	73	79	85.5	94.5	

23	76	85	91	96	
24	74	80	86.5	94.5	
25	71	79.5	87	95.5	
26	62.5	69.5	77.5	96	
27	73.5	80	87.5	91	
28	69	76.5	85.5	93.5	
29	67.5	78.5	87.5	91.5	
30	68	75.5	87	92	
31	71.5	78	86	93	
32	71	78.5	86	88	
33	68	81.5	86	93.5	
34	69	77	83.5	90.5	
35	69	78.5	85	91	
36	71.5	81.5	86.5	94	
37	70.5	77.5	82.5	88.5	
38	62.5	73	81.5	86	
39	68	76.5	82	92.5	
40	63.5	71.5	78.5	86.5	

NOTE: Table below shows the pig/pen numbers that belong to each diet treatment

DIET TYPES	DIET TREATMENTS	PIGS/PENS
LOW FAT (LF) DIET GROUP	LF CONTROL	1, 8, 12, 14, 16, 20, 21, 25
	LF PUREED	2, 5, 10, 29, 30, 38
	LF RAW DICED	6, 11, 17, 18, 27, 39
HIGH FAT (HF) DIET GROUP	HF CONTROL	3, 7, 13, 15, 28, 33, 35, 37
	HF PUREED	4, 9, 24, 26, 31, 32
	HF RAW DICED	19, 22, 23, 34, 36, 40

Appendix II. Results of the Body Weight Gain on the Weekly Basis

LFD Treatment					Weekly Weight Gain (kg)		
CONTROL					W1-Baseline	W2-Baseline	W3-Baseline
Pig No.	Baseline	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3			
1	76.5	84.5	90.5	101	8	14	24.5
8	74	84	90	91.5	10	16	17.5
12	63	72.5	81.5	88	9.5	18.5	25
14	76	84.5	91	98	8.5	15	22
16	76.5	85	92.5	99.5	8.5	16	23
20	76	81.5	94	102	5.5	18	26
21	74.5	83	90	96.5	8.5	15.5	22
25	71	79.5	87	95.5	8.5	16	24.5
Mean (kg)					8.38	16.13	23.06
SD					1.33	1.48	2.67
PUREED CARROT					Weekly Weight Gain (kg)		
Pig No.	Baseline	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	W1-Baseline	W2-Baseline	W3-Baseline
2	71	78.5	86	90	7.5	15	19
5	68.5	78.5	85	93.5	10	16.5	25
10	66.5	74.5	82	82.5	8	15.5	16
29	67.5	78.5	87.5	91.5	11	20	24
30	68	75.5	87	92	7.5	19	24
38	62.5	73	81.5	86	10.5	19	23.5
Mean (kg)					9.08	17.50	21.92
SD					1.59	2.10	3.58
RAW DICED CARROT					Weekly Weight Gain (kg)		
Pig No.	Baseline	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	W1-Baseline	W2-Baseline	W3-Baseline
6	66	73.5	78	87	7.5	12	21
11	68.5	76.5	81.5	86	8	13	17.5
17	63	70.5	75.5	83	7.5	12.5	20
18	74.5	81	87.5	95.5	6.5	13	21
27	73.5	80	87.5	91	6.5	14	17.5
39	68	76.5	82	92.5	8.5	14	24.5
Mean (kg)					7.42	13.08	20.25
SD					0.80	0.80	2.62

HFD Treatment					Weekly Weight Gain (kg)			
CONTROL					W1-Baseline	W2-Baseline	W3-Baseline	
Pig No.	Baseline	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3				
3	61.5	70.5	78.5	85.5	9	17	24	
7	74.5	81.5	86	96	7	11.5	21.5	
13	64.5	73	80	87	8.5	15.5	22.5	
15	73	82.5	90	100.5	9.5	17	27.5	
28	69	76.5	85.5	93.5	7.5	16.5	24.5	
33	68	81.5	86	93.5	13.5	18	25.5	
35	69	78.5	85	91	9.5	16	22	
37	70.5	77.5	82.5	88.5	7	12	18	
					Mean (kg)	8.94	15.44	23.19
					SD	2.11	2.40	2.88
PUREE CARROT					Weekly Weight Gain (kg)			
Pig No.	Baseline	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	W1-Baseline	W2-Baseline	W3-Baseline	
4	72	83	90	98.5	11	18	26.5	
9	69.5	78	84	86	8.5	14.5	16.5	
24	74	80	86.5	94.5	6	12.5	20.5	
26	62.5	69.5	77.5	96	7	15	33.5	
31	71.5	78	86	93	6.5	14.5	21.5	
32	71	78.5	86	88	7.5	15	17	
					Mean (kg)	7.75	14.92	22.58
					SD	1.81	1.77	6.45
RAW DICED CARROT					Weekly Weight Gain (kg)			
Pig No.	Baseline	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	W1-Baseline	W2-Baseline	W3-Baseline	
19	71	80.5	86.5	94.5	9.5	15.5	23.5	
22	73	79	85.5	94.5	6	12.5	21.5	
23	76	85	91	96	9	15	20	
34	69	77	83.5	90.5	8	14.5	21.5	
36	71.5	81.5	86.5	94	10	15	22.5	
40	63.5	71.5	78.5	86.5	8	15	23	
					Mean (kg)	8.42	14.58	22.00
					SD	1.43	1.07	1.26

NOTE: Applied to both LF and HF, the left column shows all the raw datasets, followed by the right column are the calculated weight gain on the weekly basis for each diet treatment.

Appendix III. Datasheet of Diet Particle Size Measurement / PSD (μm), NOTE: N/A = Not Available

LFD Treatment								
CONTROL : 658 μm								
Pig No.	Stomach	Jejunum	Ileum	Ascending	Transverse	Descending	Faeces	
1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	306	218	
8	8	560	284	446.5	365.25	323.5	214	
12	12	567	289.5	442.5	N/A	N/A	221	
14	14	559	286.5	456	371.25	314	207	
16	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	322.5	220	
20	20	561	290.5	443.5	367	320	213	
21	21	562	291.5	448	369.75	313	223	
25	25	569	297	448	372.5	306	219	
Mean (μm):	16.67	563.00	289.83	447.42	369.15	315.00	216.88	
SD:	6.38	4.05	4.47	4.37	2.99	7.31	5.22	
LFD Treatment								
PUREED CARROTS: 707 μm								
Pig No.	Stomach	Jejunum	Ileum	Ascending	Transverse	Descending	Faeces	
2	671.5	604	535	464.5	433	365.5	253	
5	653	613	539	470	440	362	267	
10	668.5	607	532.5	461	434.5	364	259	
29	644.5	620	545	468.5	440	356.5	253	
30	658.5	616	535	460	441.5	362	263	
38	670	603	528.5	471.5	446	355.5	252	
Mean (μm):	661.00	610.50	535.83	465.92	439.17	360.92	257.83	
SD:	10.86	6.89	5.66	4.81	4.76	4.04	6.21	
LFD Treatment								
RAW DICED CARROTS								
Pig No.	Stomach	Jejunum	Ileum	Ascending	Transverse	Descending	Faeces	
6	763	689	622.5	479.5	466	385.5	291	
11	763	697	607.5	484.5	470	388	295	
17	796	699	N/A	N/A	N/A	382.5	289	
18	782.5	701	623.5	484.5	458.5	389	296	
27	764	689	603	485	464	384	287	
39	791	709	621.5	482	463.5	379.5	298	
Mean (μm):	776.58	697.33	615.60	483.10	464.40	384.75	292.67	
SD:	15.15	7.63	9.61	2.33	4.17	3.53	4.32	

HFD Treatment								
CONTROL : 689.33 μm								
Pig No.	Stomach	Jejunum	Ileum	Ascending	Transverse	Descending	Faeces	
3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	374	228	
7	638	587	502.5	479	451	N/A	N/A	
13	631	580	510	482.5	449	385	240	
15	622.5	577	503	483	440	376.5	231	
28	632	572	498.5	487	450.5	376	237	
33	644.5	581	507	489.5	445	378	227	
35	637.5	579	504.5	481.5	449.5	377.5	248	
37	643.5	587	497	490	449	380.5	235	
Mean (μm):	635.57	580.43	503.21	484.64	447.71	378.21	235.14	
SD:	7.71	5.35	4.54	4.22	3.91	3.59	7.38	
HFD Treatment								
PUREED : 786.33 μm								
Pig No.	Stomach	Jejunum	Ileum	Ascending	Transverse	Descending	Faeces	
4	686.5	630	546.5	497.5	476.5	396	283	
9	690	646	547.5	499.5	489.5	397	287	
24	695.5	N/A	549	491.5	472.5	399	278	
26	696	631	560.5	499	484	401	281	
31	680.5	642	540.5	490.5	488.5	392	285	
32	688	626	550.5	497	479	392	276	
Mean (μm):	689.42	635.00	549.08	495.83	481.67	396.17	281.67	
SD:	5.84	8.54	6.56	3.87	6.80	3.66	4.18	
HFD Treatment								
RAW DICED CARROTS								
Pig No.	Stomach	Jejunum	Ileum	Ascending	Transverse	Descending	Faeces	
19	856.5	773	673	526.5	505.5	406.5	307	
22	N/A	784	N/A	537	509	416	304	
23	841	772	670	538	503	408	307	
34	857	787	668	532	502.5	412.5	306	
36	871	771	674	521	507	N/A	N/A	
40	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	409.5	307	
Mean (μm):	856.38	777.40	671.25	530.90	505.40	410.50	306.20	
SD:	12.26	7.50	2.75	7.18	2.72	3.79	1.30	

APPENDIX III. Equation from the Linear Fit to Work Out the Total Concentrations of Plasma Cholesterol ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)

$$\text{Concentration of Cholesterol} = (S_a/S_v) \times df^*$$

Where: S_a = Amount of cholesterol in unknown sample (μg) from standard curve
 S_v = Sample volume (μL) added into the wells_[SEP]
 C = Concentration of cholesterol in sample_[SEP]
 df^* = The dilution factor will be 201 due to the 1:200 dilution with the 1X Reaction buffer.
Cholesterol molecular weight: 386.65 g/mole.

APPENDIX IV. Total Concentrations of Plasma Cholesterol ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)

LFD Treatment		Raw Data		$x = y/236.97$		$C = (sa/sv) \times DF^*$	
CONTROL		Baseline	After Experiment (AE)	Baseline	AE	AE - Baseline	Total Cholesterol
Pig No.							
1	828	1139	3.49	4.81	1.31	5.27	
8	948	984	4.00	4.15	0.15	0.60	
12	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
14	907	1005	3.83	4.24	0.41	1.65	
16	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
20	1138	1430	4.80	6.03	1.23	4.94	
21	1001	1470	4.22	6.20	1.98	7.96	
25	1225	1727	5.17	7.29	2.12	8.52	
Mean ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$):							4.82
SD:							3.21
PUREED CARROT							
Pig No.							
2	640	1144	2.70	4.83	2.13	8.56	
5	1004	1125	4.24	4.75	0.51	2.05	
10	941	1148	3.97	4.84	0.87	3.50	
29	910	1004	3.84	4.24	0.40	1.61	
30	897	976	3.79	4.12	0.33	1.33	
38	962	1331	4.06	5.62	1.56	6.27	
Mean ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$):							3.89
SD:							2.93
RAW DICED CARROTS							
Pig No.							
6	955	1123	4.03	4.74	0.71	2.85	
11	981	1303	4.14	5.50	1.36	5.47	
17	578	1039	2.44	4.38	1.95	7.84	
18	1535	1571	6.48	6.63	0.15	0.60	
27	1009	1171	4.26	4.94	0.68	2.73	
39	1035	1097	4.37	4.63	0.26	1.05	
Mean ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$):							3.42
SD:							2.76

HFD Treatment							
CONTROL							
	Raw Data		$x = y/236.97$		$C = (sa/sv) \times DF^*$		
Pig No.	Baseline	After Experiment (AE)	Baseline	AE	AE - Baseline	Total Cholesterol	
3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
7	571	1248	2.41	5.27	2.86	11.50	
13	1054	1487	4.45	6.28	1.83	7.36	
15	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
28	1070	1756	4.52	7.41	2.89	11.62	
33	975	1118	4.11	4.72	0.60	2.41	
35	969	1016	4.09	4.29	0.20	0.80	
37	1420	1494	5.99	6.30	0.31	1.25	
Mean ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$):						5.83	
SD:						5.02	
PUREED CARROT							
Pig No.	Baseline	After Experiment (AE)	Baseline	AE	AE - Baseline	Total Cholesterol	
4	1116	1247	4.71	5.26	0.55	2.21	
9	994	1236	4.19	5.22	1.02	4.10	
24	888	1593	3.75	6.72	2.98	11.98	
26	1256	1411	5.30	5.95	0.65	2.61	
31	1138	1262	4.80	5.33	0.52	2.09	
32	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Mean ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$):						4.62	
SD:						4.20	
RAW DICED CARROT							
Pig No.	Baseline	After Experiment (AE)	Baseline	AE	AE - Baseline	Total Cholesterol	
19	1077	1391	4.54	5.87	1.33	5.35	
22	1083	1118	4.57	4.72	0.15	0.60	
23	1137	1658	4.80	7.00	2.20	8.84	
34	1176	1413	4.96	5.96	1.00	4.02	
36	941	1064	3.97	4.49	0.52	2.09	
40	1133	1266	4.78	5.34	0.56	2.25	
Mean ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$):						3.86	
SD:						2.95	

NOTE: Total concentrations of plasma cholesterol are calculated based on the linear fits from fluorescence RFU vs. standard cholesterol concentrations. Means are expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ originally, and $(\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}) \times 100$ to get mg/dL as expressed in the result section. N/A: Not Analyse.